
ON DISCRETE DISLOCATIONS & THE DEVELOPMENT OF
AN INTEGRAL REPRESENTATION FOR THE ELASTIC
ENERGY IN THE CONTINUUM LIMIT

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Abstract

This thesis focuses on the study of a recently developed theory of a fully discrete model of dislocations in crystal structures, making use of algebraic topology and exterior differential calculus. From this discrete model of crystal, we define the elastic energy induced by dislocation forming strains in a two dimensional triangular lattice and study its properties. Reviewing recent results, we prove that the elastic energy of grains formed by two infinite parallel walls of dislocation dipoles satisfies the well known Read-Shockley law. Furthermore, we study the elastic energy of grain inducing dislocations with variable lattice spacing in the underlying triangular lattice, and discuss its Γ -limit as the lattice spacing goes to zero. Considering an ansatz for the Γ -limit of the rescaled energy, we prove that it is additive under a specific set of dislocations. In particular, we make progress in showing that the limiting energy of the scaled elastic energy functional, as the lattice spacing goes to zero, has a sought after integral representation that is dependent on a surface energy density.

Key words: *Calculus of Variations, Discrete Dislocation Mechanics, Crystal Defects.*

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The study of material properties and how they are affected by defects within their structure has been of much interest to the scientific and mathematical communities in recent years. In particular, defects known as *dislocations* in the material structure have been at the heart of a number of studies of this form (see [AO05; AO10; GT19; LL16; CGM15; Bul+06] and references therein). This research has been motivated by the understanding that the presence of *dislocations* in materials is the main mechanism behind plastic deformation, where after a material is deformed, it does not return to its original shape. Furthermore, dislocations are also known to cause *strain hardening*, where their presence through a continuous deformation of the material, increases its strength, see [FBZ80].

The materials of interest in this thesis shall be those of *crystalline* form. A material is considered to be crystalline in nature if its constituent atoms are arranged in a pattern that repeats itself periodically in space. Many materials, including some metals, exhibit this specific structure. The three most common periodic structures in crystals are *body-centred cubic* (BCC), which are present in Iron and Chromium, *face-centred cubic* (FCC), present in Copper, Aluminium, and Gold, and *close-packed hexagonal* (CPH), see Figure 1.1 for a visual representation of these three types of structures. Although some metals have a crystalline atomic form, in general, metals in the real world and the ones used in industry often do not exhibit periodic behaviour at long range, and instead, their atomic structure is disturbed by the presence of defects, as discussed above.

1.1 Dislocations

Dislocations are an important class of defects in materials which are defined as one dimensional topological defects present in crystal structures. There are a number of texts which deal with the topic of dislocations; two popular introductory texts into this field include [HL92; HB11]. The study of dislocations goes back to the 1930's where they were first rigorously proposed to solve the discrepancy in the theoretical and experimental strengths of

Figure 1.1: Three most common types of lattice structures for crystals. Source: http://www.ggsptd.com/uploads/8/1/0/4/81043910/8970374_orig.png.

materials. As a result, these investigations brought together the practical and theoretical results for the values of the applied stress required to plastically deform some materials. A concise history into the study of dislocations in its early stages is given in [Hir85].

Geometrically speaking, dislocations in crystals form via the presence or absence of an extra layer of atoms in its crystal structure. The most useful definition, in the sense of geometrical understanding, of a dislocation is given via the definition of a *Burgers circuit*. A Burgers circuit, in a lattice with defects, is a closed lattice valued path around a patch of the lattice. If one then repeats the path of the Burgers circuit in a perfect analogue of the lattice with defects, and the path does not perfectly close, i.e. it is either too long or too short, then the existence of at least one dislocation within the region bounded by the Burgers circuit is implied. Assuming that the circuit does not perfectly close, the vector that is required to perfectly close the circuit is known as the *Burgers vector*. This vector field theory based approach to defining dislocations, where the Burgers vector describes the local difference in slip caused by the presence of a dislocation, was introduced by Burgers in his landmark paper [Bur95]. In three dimensions, there are two fundamental types of dislocations, which make up any general dislocation, known as *edge* and *screw* dislocations. A dislocation is known to be an edge or a screw dislocation if its Burgers vector is perpendicular or, respectively parallel to its dislocation line, where a dislocation line is defined as the line of atoms within the crystal along which the Burgers vector, deduced via a Burgers circuit, is conserved. A visual representation of this discussion is given in Figure 1.2.

The understanding of defects such as dislocations is of fundamental importance to engineers, since their presence in a material strongly influences its properties. Dislocations

Figure 1.2: Depiction of an edge and screw dislocation on an imperfect cubic lattice. The bold black lines represent the *dislocation lines*, the grey arrowed lines represent the *Burgers circuit* and the blue arrows represent the *Burgers vector's* of the dislocations present. Source: Figure 1.2 from [Hud14].

in materials can form through a number of mechanisms, two notable mechanisms are: via the application of a substantial stress to a material which causes it to plastically deform, and via lattice misfits, for example at the boundary between two adjacent connected lattices which have different lattice spacings. In the presence of lattice misfits, dislocations form to minimise the total elastic energy of the material. See Figure 1.3 for an example of the formation of dislocations at the boundary between a Silicon and Nickel Silicide lattices.

The mechanism for the formation of dislocation via an application of stress is described as follows. Consider a perfect, defect free, lattice in its ground state. If one applies a very small force on this material such as not to cause any bonds between atoms to break, then the material deforms in such a way that when the applied stress is removed, the material will return to its original shape; this is known as *elastic deformation*. If instead a sufficient force is applied to the material such that the layers within its crystal structure are caused to move with respect to one another and form new bonds with now neighbouring atoms, i.e. *slip*, then this can lead to *plastic deformation*, where the material will no longer return to its original shape when the applied stress is removed. If higher and higher stresses are applied to the material, then the crystal layers will further be forced to slip, and eventually the material will *fracture*, where the stress has caused the material to split. This type of phenomenon is readily observed in the real world, and lattice slips like those discussed above can be seen to form in a rod of Cadmium in Figure 1.4 that has been stretched along its axis.

Many metals exhibit a *polycrystalline form* in which the atomic structure of the metal is composed of a number of interacting sublattices, known as *grains*, that are mutually rotated with respect to one another and are connected by two dimensional defects known

Figure 1.3: Left: Dislocation (shown at the end of the orange line of atoms) at the boundary between two lattices of different line spacing. The red dotted lines show the atomic bonds connecting the two different misaligned lattices. Right: Formation of dislocations due to lattice misfits caused in a composite material of Nickel Silicide (NiSi) and Silicon (Si); Source: https://www.tf.uni-kiel.de/matwis/amat/semitech_en/kap_3/illustr/misfit_dislocations.gif.

as *grain boundaries*. Grain boundaries form as a result of the misalignment between adjacent sublattices, and are composed of a collection of dislocations that are present as to minimise the energy of the material. The presence of grain boundaries can also affect the properties of the material, e.g. its electrical and thermal conductivity. See Figure 1.5 for a photograph of a section of a Iron-Carbon alloy for an example of a polycrystalline material.

The energy of a grain boundary is defined as the excess free energy associated with the presence of a grain boundary, with the background perfect lattice as a reference point. It has been shown by [RS50] that the energy of a grain boundary, formed as a result of a small angle, θ , difference between adjacent grains, is predicted by the Read-Shockley law

$$E_0\theta(A_0 - \log \theta), \quad (1.1)$$

where E_0, A_0 are two constants that depend on the material properties. The energy of grain boundaries that form θ is large is a much more complex scenario, where there is no strong general theory in place as there is when θ is small. There have been a number of recent studies regarding the energy of grain boundaries that have formed as a result of a small angle mutual rotation, see [LL16; Fan18].

1.2 Dislocation Models

Classically, dislocations have often been studied under the continuum assumption of materials, where the atomic scale is introduced as an internal scale with something known as a *core radius*. However, these continuum models are limited by the amount of information about the material structure that they can contain. Since, in the continuum model, the positions of the atoms are considered in a probabilistic sense, i.e. they are averaged out,

Figure 1.4: Scanning electron microscope photograph of a Cadmium crystal being deformed along the structure to show the formation of slip steps along its structure. The first image on the left shows the Cadmium rod under no stress, whereas the second and third images show Cadmium under stress along its structure. Source: https://www.doitpoms.ac.uk/tlplib/slip/slip_in_hcp4.php.

many degrees of freedom, such as the atomic bonds, slip planes, dislocation lines and the way the clumps of atoms deform, are lost. Furthermore, under a core radius approach of a dislocation, the lattice structure about a dislocation is modelled very poorly. To tackle these problems, recent developments by [AO05] have allowed for the study of dislocations at the exact atomic scale, where many of the degrees of freedom that we expect to consider in our model are taken into account. This has enabled a more precise study of crystal defects. The key tools that have allowed for this to happen is the incorporation of elements of algebraic topology and exterior differential calculus into the model. This novel approach is reviewed in Chapter 2 of this thesis, and shall be the main model behind which we study dislocations. Another discrete model of crystal defects has been formulated in [LM10], although it is of less relevance to the topic of this thesis.

Using this fully discrete model of crystal mechanics, we can consider a two dimensional lattice $\varepsilon\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, where $\varepsilon > 0$ denotes the lattice spacing, and on this, approximate the elastic energy of a material under a strain ξ , acting on pairs of atoms, by

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{x \sim y} [\xi(x, y) \cdot (x - y)]^2, \quad (1.2)$$

where $x, y \in \varepsilon\mathcal{L}$ are lattice points and $x \sim y$ indicates that they are adjacent (i.e. the energy only considers nearest neighbour interactions). When studying dislocation models, it is of interest to determine the Γ -limit of the energy (1.2) (up to a scaling) as the lattice spacing ε tends to zero, in order to obtain a continuum model of dislocations. A fundamental question regarding the Γ -limit is whether it has an integral representation of the form:

$$\mathcal{E}(\mu) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \gamma \left(n(x), \frac{\mu}{|\mu|}(x) \right) d\mu(x), \quad \mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2), \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 1.5: A photograph of a section of a hypereutectoid Iron-Carbon alloy having a polycrystalline structure. The white lines in the image depict the grain boundaries. Source: <https://www.doitpoms.ac.uk/tlplib/atomic-scale-structure/images/hypereutectoid.jpg>.

for some surface function $\gamma : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ and normal $n : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, where μ denotes the distribution of a dislocation. The paper [Pon07] deals with precisely this question under the discrete formalism introduced by [AO05], although under a different lattice considered in this thesis. When \mathcal{L} denotes a triangular lattice, whether the Γ -limit of the rescaled energy function (1.2) has an integral representation of the form (1.3) is not yet known, and this shall be the main driving factor of the material in this thesis. In order to prove that the continuum energy, obtained from a fully discrete model as above, has the specific integral representation given above, a possibility is to make use of an integral representation theorem, like that from [BB92]. The authors of [BB92] state that if the limiting energy is additive under singular measures and weakly lower semicontinuous, then the limiting energy functional has a specific integral representation. In Chapter 4 of this thesis, we prove intermediate results regarding the additivity of the Γ -limit, which highly suggests that the limiting energy does indeed have a form very similar to that of (1.3). To the best knowledge of the author, the additivity result of Lemma 4.4 has not yet been demonstrated in the literature for two dimensional triangular lattices.

1.3 Structure of Thesis

The thesis is structured in the following way. In Chapter 2, we discuss the discrete model of crystal mechanics developed by [AO05] which allows us to study dislocations directly at the atomic scale. In the discrete model, we take into consideration many degrees of freedom that are normally ignored in continuum models, such as atomic bonds. In Chapter 3, using the Ariza-Ortiz model of dislocations developed in Chapter 2, following the work of [GT19], we study the Hamiltonian of the elastic energy of dislocations and

obtain the energy of a grain boundary that is formed in a two dimensional triangular lattice. In Chapter 4, we begin a scaling analysis of the Ariza-Ortiz energy by considering an arbitrary lattice spacing. We then prove that under certain types of dislocations, the limiting energy obtained as the lattice spacing goes to zero, satisfies an additivity property. In particular, we make progress in showing that the limiting energy of the scaled elastic energy, as the lattice spacing goes to zero, has a sought after integral representation of the form (1.3). To the best knowledge of the author, the additivity result has not yet been demonstrated in the literature for two dimensional triangular lattices. Finally, in Chapter 5, we conclude on the work of this thesis and provide possible avenues for future research on the topics discussed.

Chapter 2

Discrete Model of Crystal Mechanics

We begin the thesis by first describing the discrete model of crystal mechanics recently developed by [AO05]. Here, we describe the discrete model of crystal mechanics that we will use to describe defects, such as dislocations, in crystal lattices. This particular model of crystal mechanics relies on elements of algebraic topology and differential calculus, which have been used to streamline the notation and give insight into the structure of the mathematical theory. Some details have been omitted due to their irrelevance, but for a full account of this model we refer the reader to [AO05]. Furthermore, for an introduction on the topic of algebraic topology, we refer to the texts [Hat02; BT82], which should provide the necessary material for the content discussed in this chapter.

The theory of the discrete model of crystal mechanics wholly relies on the assumption that the domain in which our mathematics is carried out on is of lattice type. An elementary view of a crystal lattice is that simply of a point set, where each site is occupied by an atom. Although, this is a relatively naive way of trying to model the real world since many important aspects of lattices, such as bonds between atoms, are ignored. Therefore, for a more complete view of crystal lattice, we include objects such as atomic bonds, elementary areas and elementary volumes, as depicted in a model square lattice in Figure 2.1. The more complete lattice is now referred to as a *complex lattice*, and an element of algebraic topology is introduced to simplify notation and calculations in later chapters.

2.1 Crystal Complexes

We begin by regarding crystal lattices as *chain complexes* in the sense of algebraic topology. We develop the chain complex theory of crystal lattices in the underlying space $X = \mathbb{R}^n$ where $n \in \{2, 3\}$, although in later chapters, we shall restrict to the case when $n = 2$ for simplicity.¹ For brevity, let \mathcal{B}^p denote the unit p -dimensional ball in \mathbb{R}^p for

¹Generalisations to higher dimensions, i.e. $n > 3$, can be made with relative easy.

Figure 2.1: Left: depiction of an elementary view of a simple square lattice which is represented as the point set $\{a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, where $e_1 = (1, 0)^T$ and $e_2 = (0, 1)^T$. Right: depiction of a *complex lattice*, where the black dots represent the 0-cells (i.e. atoms), the blue lines the 1-cells (i.e. atomic bonds) and the grey shaded region represents a 2-cell.

$p \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$. Now, we begin with the definition of a fundamental object in a complex crystal, i.e. a *cell*.

Definition 2.1 (Cell)

A space e_p is called a *p-cell*, or *cell of dimension* $p \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, if it is homeomorphic to \mathcal{B}^p , i.e. there exists a continuous and bijective function $f : e_p \rightarrow \mathcal{B}^p$ such that f^{-1} is also continuous. We call a cell *open* if it is homeomorphic to $\text{Int } \mathcal{B}^p$. We define the orientation of *p-cells* in the following way:

- 0-cells have only one orientation;
- 1-cells have an orientation dependent on the ordering of its corresponding 0-cells. Let $[x, y]$ denote a generic 1-cell with corresponding 0-cells x, y . We say that two adjacent oriented 1-cells are oriented consistently, if the two cells are of the form $[x, y]$ and $[y, z]$ for 0-cells x, y, z ;
- 2-cells have an orientation dependent on a reference vector n which is orthogonal to the 2-cell, where its corresponding 1-cells are consistently oriented with respect to the right hand rule;
- 3-cells are either oriented *inwards* or *outwards*: its faces are said to be consistently oriented if their reference vectors all point, correspondingly, in the outward or inward directions.

To each *p-cell* we impose on it the above orientation, and denote by E_p the set of all **oriented** *p-cells*.

We are now in a position to give the definition of an *n-dimensional lattice complex*, which we shall sometimes refer to as a *complex lattice*, where $n \in \{2, 3\}$ will be assumed throughout, unless stated otherwise.

Figure 2.2: Depiction of oriented p -cells, with $p = 1, 2$, from left to right. The notation \odot corresponds to the reference vector of the 2-cell pointing out of the paper; this corresponds to the well known right hand rule for the direction of a magnetic field around current carrying wire.

Definition 2.2 (Lattice Complex)

We define an n -dimensional lattice complex X to be a CW complex such that

- (i) The underlying space is \mathbb{R}^n ;
- (ii) The vertex set E_0 defines a *classical* lattice;²
- (iii) The cell sets E_p , for $p = 0, \dots, n$ are translation and symmetry invariant.³

Remark 2.3

- In Definition 2.2, we make a slight abuse of notation, where we state that X denotes both the complex and the underlying space of the complex. This shall be repeated throughout unless explicitly stated otherwise.
- The requirement that elements of the complex X form a CW complex gives mathematical meaning to the fact that we expect our cells to be non-intersecting, and their boundaries are formed via cells of lower dimension.

From now on, unless otherwise stated, denote by X a lattice complex with underlying space \mathbb{R}^n and let G denote an abelian group (e.g. $G = \mathbb{R}^m$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$).

Definition 2.4 (Chain)

A G -valued p -chain in a lattice complex X is a homomorphism $c_p : E_p \rightarrow G$ such that

- (i) $c_p(e_p) = -c_p(e'_p)$ if e_p and e'_p are opposite orientations of the same cell in E_p ;
- (ii) $c_p(e_p) = 0$ for all but finitely many oriented p -cells $e_p \in E_p$.

Now let C_p denote the set of all oriented p -chains, i.e.

$$C_p := \{ c_p : E_p \rightarrow G \mid c_p \text{ is a } p\text{-chain} \}.$$

²This means that it is a set of the form $\{ \sum_{i=1}^n n_i a_i \mid n_i \in \mathbb{Z}^n \}$ where $(a_i)_{i=1}^n$ denotes a set of basis vectors.

³A *CW complex* is a space formed by *gluing* cells of lower order to construct higher order cells. See [Hat02] or [AO05] for a detailed description.

Furthermore, for a cell $e_p \in E_p$, the corresponding elementary chain, which we shall denote by a boldface letter, $\mathbf{e}_p : E_p \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ is a p -chain such that for $e \in E_p$

$$\mathbf{e}_p(e) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } e = e_p, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Remark 2.5

In addition to Definition 2.4, if $p < 0$ or if $p > n$, $C_p = \{0\}$, i.e. the trivial group.

Now, once the cells have been oriented accordingly, a p -chain $c_p \in C_p$ can be written *uniquely* as a finite linear combination of elementary chains, i.e.

$$c_p = \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_i \mathbf{e}_i, \quad \alpha_i \in G \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, n.$$

This implies that the space C_p is a *free-abelian group*. Given the decomposition of p -chains into elementary chains, we may define the following boundary operator on elementary chains.

Notation: For cells $e_p \in E_p$, we say that $e_{p-1} \prec e_p$ if e_{p-1} is a boundary cell of e_p .

Definition 2.6 (Boundary Operator)

The *boundary operator* $\partial_p : C_p \rightarrow C_{p-1}$ is a homomorphism defined as

$$\partial_p \mathbf{e}_p = \sum_{e_{p-1} \prec e_p} \pm \mathbf{e}_{p-1},$$

where the sign is chosen as $+$ (or $-$) if the orientation of e_{p-1} coincides (respectively, the opposite of) that induced by e_p . Recall that $C_{-1} = \{0\}$, thus $\partial_0 : C_0 \rightarrow C_{-1}$ is a zero mapping. Furthermore, since $C_{n+1} = \{0\}$, it makes sense to define $\partial_{n+1} = 0$. Given the definition above and also the fact that any p -chain can be written uniquely as a combination of elementary p -chains, the operator ∂_p extends uniquely to be define on the whole of C_p .

Proposition 2.7

Let $\partial_p : C_p \rightarrow C_{p-1}$ be the boundary operator on a chain complex X . Then

$$\partial_{p-1} \partial_p = 0 \quad \forall p = 0, \dots, n.$$

Proof. Let $e_p \in E_p$ be an oriented p -cell and let \mathbf{e}_p denote its corresponding elementary

chain. Then

$$\partial_{p-1}\partial_p\mathbf{e}_p = \sum_{e_{p-1} \prec e_p} \left(\pm \sum_{e_{p-2} \prec e_{p-1}} \pm \mathbf{e}_{p-2} \right),$$

and the terms in these two sums cancel in pairs, which yields the desired result. \square

Definition 2.8 (Homology Group)

Let $\partial_p : C_p \rightarrow C_{p-1}$ be the boundary operator on a chain complex X , then

- (i) $Z_p := \ker \partial_p$ is called the group of p -cycles;
- (ii) $B_p := \text{im } \partial_{p+1}$ is called the group of p -boundaries;
- (iii) $H_p := Z_p/B_p$ is called the p th homology group of the lattice complex.⁴

Definition 2.9 (Perfect Lattice Complex)

We say that a lattice complex is *perfect/defect free* if its homology group is identical to the homology group of the underlying space. Since the underlying space of X is \mathbb{R}^n , then X is said to be perfect if

$$H_p = \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z} & \text{if } p = 0; \\ \{0\} & \text{if } p = 1, \dots, n. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.10 (Cochain)

We define the group C^p of p -cochains as the group of all homomorphisms of C_p into G ,

$$C^p := \text{Hom}(C_p, G).$$

We denote by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : C^p \times C_p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the duality pairing between C^p and C_p . Furthermore, the adjoint operator $*$: $C_p \rightarrow C^p$ defines an isomorphism, where we shall denote its inverse also by $*$. Therefore, any elementary chain \mathbf{e}_p has a unique cochain representation $\mathbf{e}^p := (\mathbf{e}_p)^*$, and vice-versa.

Definition 2.11 (Coboundary Operator)

The *coboundary operator* $\delta^p : C^p \rightarrow C^{p+1}$ is defined by the identity

$$\langle \delta^p c^p, c_{p+1} \rangle := \langle c^p, \partial_{p+1} c_{p+1} \rangle \quad \text{for } c_p \in C_p, c^p \in C^p.$$

In particular, it denotes the *adjoint* of the boundary operator, and thus also has the following homomorphism representation

$$\delta^p \mathbf{e}^p = \sum_{e_{p+1} \succ e_p} \pm \mathbf{e}^{p+1},$$

⁴What survives in H_p are the p -dimensional *holes*, i.e. those p -cycles that are not p -boundaries.

where the sign is chosen as $+$ (or $-$) if the orientation of e_p coincides with (respectively, is the opposite of) that induces by e_{p+1} .

Proposition 2.12

Let $\delta^p : C^p \rightarrow C^{p+1}$ be the coboundary operator on a chain complex X , then

$$\delta^{p+1}\delta^p = 0 \quad \forall p = 0, \dots, n.$$

Proof. Let $e_p \in E_p$ denote an oriented p -cell, and let \mathbf{e}^p denote its corresponding p -cochain. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \delta^{p+1}\delta^p \mathbf{e}^p, \mathbf{e}_{p+2} \rangle &= \langle \delta^p \mathbf{e}^p, \partial_{p+2} \mathbf{e}_{p+2} \rangle \\ &= \langle \mathbf{e}^p, \partial_{p+1} \partial_{p+2} \mathbf{e}_{p+2} \rangle \\ &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows from the fact that $\partial_{p+1}\partial_{p+2} = 0$, see Proposition 2.7. Since this holds for an arbitrary p -cell e_p , this holds for all p -cochains, as required. \square

Analogously to the boundary operator, we may also define a *homology* group for the coboundary operator, which we shall call the *cohomology group*.

Definition 2.13 (Cohomology Group)

Let $\delta^p : C^p \rightarrow C^{p+1}$ denote the coboundary operator on a chain complex X , then

- (i) $Z^p := \ker \delta^p$ is called the group of *p -cocycles*;
- (ii) $B^p := \text{im } \delta^{p-1}$ is called the group of *p -coboundaries*;
- (iii) $H^p := Z^p/B^p$ is called the *p th cohomology group of the lattice complex*.

2.2 Exterior Differential Calculus

Having now given a brief introduction to the theory of lattice mechanics, we are now in a position to extend this theory and develop a complex lattice analogue of the de Rham complex in \mathbb{R}^n and thus a discrete version of exterior differential calculus, which shall become essential in later chapters.

As in the previous subsection, consider a lattice complex $X = (E_p)_{p=0}^n$ with the underlying space \mathbb{R}^n and its corresponding chain complex $\{C_p, \partial_p\}$. We now define a fundamental object, and an extension of cochains defined in the previous subsection, *forms*. Let G denote an arbitrary abelian group (e.g. of the form \mathbb{R}^m , $m \in \mathbb{N}$).

Definition 2.14 (Differential Forms)

An abelian group G valued exterior differential form of order p , or a p -form, is a cochain with coefficients that lie in G . We denote the set of p -forms over X with coefficients in G as $\Omega^p(X, G)$. Thus, given that a p -cochain has a representation in terms of elementary p -cochains, any p -form $\omega \in \Omega^p(X, G)$ has the representation

$$\omega = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \mathbf{e}^p,$$

where $f : E_p \rightarrow G$. The value of a p -form on a general p -chain $c_p \in C_p$ is

$$\langle \omega, c_p \rangle := \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \langle \mathbf{e}^p, c_p \rangle.$$

When it is understood on what complex a form is defined on and what space a form is taking values in, we simply refer to the set of p -forms as Ω^p . Unless otherwise stated, let $\Omega^p := \Omega^p(X, G)$.

Definition 2.15 (Exterior Derivative)

We define the *exterior derivative* $d^p : \Omega^p \rightarrow \Omega^{p+1}$ as homomorphism such that for any p -form $\omega \in \Omega^p$, $d^p \omega \in \Omega^{p+1}$ the $(p+1)$ -form such that

$$d^p \omega = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \delta^p \mathbf{e}^p.$$

Proposition 2.16

Let $d^p : \Omega^p \rightarrow \Omega^{p+1}$ be the exterior derivative of forms. Then

$$d^{p+1} d^p = 0 \quad \forall p = 0, \dots, n.$$

Proof. Let $\omega \in \Omega^p$ denote a general p -form. Then

$$\begin{aligned} d^{p+1} d^p \omega &= d^{p+1} \left(\sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \delta^p \mathbf{e}^p \right) \\ &= \sum_{e_p \in E_p} d^{p+1} (f(e_p) \delta^p \mathbf{e}^p) \\ &= \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \delta^{p+1} \delta^p \mathbf{e}^p = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows since $\delta^{p+1} \delta^p = 0$, see Proposition 2.12, which is precisely as was required. \square

For brevity, when the dimensions of the functions is understood, we denote the exterior

derivative simply as d .

Definition 2.17 (de Rham Complex)

The exterior derivative d together with the graded algebra $\Omega^* := \bigoplus_{p=0}^n \Omega^p$ define the *de Rham complex* on the lattice complex X .

Definition 2.18 (Closed and Exact Forms)

Let (d, Ω^*) denote a de Rham complex on a lattice complex X .

- (i) A form $\alpha \in \Omega^p$ is *closed* if $d\alpha = 0$;
- (ii) A form $\alpha \in \Omega^p$ is *exact* if there exists a form $\beta \in \Omega^{p-1}$ such that $\alpha = d\beta$.

Definition 2.19 (de Rham Cohomology)

The p th *de Rham cohomology* of the lattice complex X is the vector space

$$H^p := (\ker d \cap \Omega^p) / (\text{im } d \cap \Omega^p).$$

The *cohomology* of the lattice complex X is the direct sum $H^* := \bigoplus_{p \in \mathbb{Z}} H^p$.

We now state a fundamental result of exterior differential calculus, now stated in the sense of discrete differential calculus.

Lemma 2.20 (Poincaré Lemma)

Let H^* denote the cohomology of the lattice complex $X = \mathbb{R}^n$. Then

$$H^* = \begin{cases} \mathbb{R} & \text{if } n = 0, \\ \{0\} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Remark 2.21

Poincaré's lemma, Lemma 2.20, states that if the underlying space is \mathbb{R}^n , then in the case that $n \geq 1$, all closed forms are exact. Thus, we require the cohomology of a *perfect* n -dimensional lattice to be identical to that of \mathbb{R}^n .

Now, considerations of duality lead naturally to the definition of p -vector fields and the *codifferential operator*.

Definition 2.22 (Vector Fields)

A G -valued vector field of order p , or a *p -vector field* is G -valued chain with a arbitrary (not necessarily finite) support. We denote the set of G -valued p -vector fields over X as $\Omega_p(X, G)$. As with forms, we denote this set by Ω_p when the working spaces are well understood. Thus, p -vector fields, $u \in \Omega_p$, have the representation

$$u := \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \mathbf{e}_p,$$

where $f : E_p \rightarrow G$. By the definition of p -forms on p -chains, if $u = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p)\mathbf{e}_p \in \Omega_p$ and $\alpha = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} g(e_p)\mathbf{e}^p \in \Omega^p$, then

$$\langle \alpha, u \rangle = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} \langle f(e_p), g(e_p) \rangle_G,$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_G$ is the inner product with respect to the space G .

Remark 2.23

Throughout this thesis, we deal with the situation where $G = \mathbb{R}^n = X$, and thus deal with forms and vector fields which have coefficients in a Hilbert space \mathbb{R}^n under the standard L^2 -inner product. Therefore, from now on, for forms $\alpha = \sum f e^p$, $\beta = \sum g e^p$ and vector fields $u = \sum a e_p$, $v = \sum b e_p$ which take valued in a Hilbert space, their corresponding L^2 -inner products are

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle &= \sum_{e_p \in E_p} \langle f(e_p), g(e_p) \rangle_{L^2}, \\ \langle u, v \rangle &= \sum_{e_p \in E_p} \langle a(e_p), b(e_p) \rangle_{L^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\langle p, q \rangle_{L^2} = p \cdot q$ for $p, q \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Definition 2.24 (Codifferential Operator)

We define the *codifferential operator* $(d^{p-1})^* : \Omega_p \rightarrow \Omega_{p-1}$ by the identity

$$\langle \alpha, (d^{p-1})^* u \rangle = \langle d^p \alpha, u \rangle \quad \forall \alpha \in \Omega^{p-1}, u \in \Omega_p,$$

which, for $u = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p)\mathbf{e}_p$, admits the follow representation

$$(d^{p-1})^* u = \sum_{e_p \in E_p} f(e_p) \partial_p \mathbf{e}_p.$$

Proposition 2.25

Let $(d^{p-1})^* : \Omega_p \rightarrow \Omega_{p-1}$ be the codifferential operator. Then

$$(d^{p-2})^* (d^{p-1})^* = 0 \quad \forall p = 0, \dots, n.$$

Proof. The proof is analogous to Proposition 2.16 and makes use of Proposition 2.12. \square

From now on, as with d , denote by d^* the codifferential operator when the dimension is well understood. We now define the discrete calculus equivalent of the Laplacian, which will become a vital tool in allowing to determine whether our lattice is perfect or not.

Definition 2.26 (Laplace de Rham Operator)

We define the *discrete Laplace de Rham operator* $\Delta_p : \Omega^p \rightarrow \Omega^p$ by the formula

$$\Delta_p := d^{p-1}(d^{p-1})^* + (d^p)^*d^p,$$

although, we shall often use the notation Δ when the dimension p is known, and shall often make use of the generalised definition $\Delta = dd^* + d^*d$.

Lemma 2.27

The Laplace-de Rham operator Δ commutes with the exterior derivative d and the codifferential operator d^ , i.e.*

$$d\Delta = \Delta d \quad \text{and} \quad d^*\Delta = \Delta d^*.$$

Proof. Applying the definition Δ and using Proposition 2.16, we have that

$$d\Delta = d(dd^* + d^*d) = d^2d^* + dd^*d = dd^*d = (dd^* + d^*d)d = \Delta d.$$

The proof for the codifferential operator is analogous but instead using Proposition 2.25. \square

Definition 2.28 (Harmonic Forms)

A form $\alpha \in \Omega^p$ is called *harmonic* if $\Delta\alpha = 0$. Let K^p denote the vector space of all harmonic p -forms.

Proposition 2.29

For any $\gamma \in \Omega^p$, $\Delta\gamma = 0$ if and only if $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^\gamma = 0$.*

Proof. Let $\gamma \in \Omega^p$. Then if $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^*\gamma = 0$, by the definition of Δ , it is clear that $\Delta\gamma = 0$. Conversely, if $\Delta\gamma = 0$, then

$$0 = \langle \Delta\gamma, \gamma \rangle = \langle dd^*\gamma, \gamma \rangle + \langle d^*d\gamma, \gamma \rangle = \langle d^*\gamma, d^*\gamma \rangle + \langle d\gamma, d\gamma \rangle,$$

whence it follows that $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^*\gamma = 0$, as required. \square

Theorem 2.30 (Hodge Decomposition Theorem)

For $p \in \{0, \dots, n\}$, we may decompose Ω^p as

$$\Omega^p = d\Omega^{p-1} \oplus d^*\Omega^{p+1} \oplus K^p,$$

where the decomposition is L^2 -orthogonal.

Proof. It is clear that $d\Omega^{p-1} \oplus d^*\Omega^{p+1} \oplus K^p \subseteq \Omega^p$, thus it remains to show the opposite

inclusion. Let $\alpha \in \Omega^{p-1}$, $\beta \in \Omega^{p+1}$ and $\gamma \in K^p$. Now, $d\Omega^{p-1}$ is orthogonal to $d^*\Omega^{p+1}$ since

$$\langle d\alpha, d^*\beta \rangle = \langle d^2\alpha, \beta \rangle = 0.$$

Furthermore, since $\gamma \in K^p$, we have that $\Delta\gamma = 0$. But, by Proposition 2.29, $\Delta\gamma = 0$ if and only if $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^*\gamma = 0$, thus, it follows that

$$\langle d\alpha, \gamma \rangle = \langle \alpha, d^*\gamma \rangle = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle d^*\beta, \gamma \rangle = \langle \beta, d\gamma \rangle = 0,$$

in particular that $d\Omega^{p-1}$ and $d^*\Omega^{p+1}$ are orthogonal to K^p , respectively. Therefore, the spaces $d\Omega^{p-1}$, $d^*\Omega^{p+1}$ and K^p are pairwise orthogonal. Let $\mathcal{C}^p := (d\Omega^{p-1} \oplus d^*\Omega^{p+1})^\perp$. To complete the proof, it suffices to show that $\mathcal{C}^p \equiv K^p$. It is clear that $K^p \subseteq \mathcal{C}^p$. Conversely, let $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}^p$. Then by the definition of \mathcal{C}^p

$$\langle \alpha, d^*\gamma \rangle = \langle d\alpha, \gamma \rangle = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \beta, d\gamma \rangle = \langle d^*\beta, \gamma \rangle = 0 \quad \forall \alpha \in \Omega^{p-1}, \forall \beta \in \Omega^{p+1}.$$

In particular $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^*\gamma = 0$, thus, by Proposition 2.29, $\Delta\gamma = 0$, i.e. $\gamma \in K^p$. Therefore $\mathcal{C}^p \subseteq K^p$, which concludes the proof. \square

Corollary 2.31

The spaces K^p and the p th de Rham cohomology H^p are isomorphic.

Proof. Let $\gamma \in K^p$, then $\Delta\gamma = 0$ and thus $d\gamma = 0$, hence $\gamma \in \ker d^p$. Therefore, there exists an inclusion mapping $\iota : K^p \hookrightarrow \ker d^p$. Furthermore, projecting $\ker d^p$ onto H^p via the mapping $\mathbb{P} : \ker d^p \rightarrow H^p; \gamma \mapsto [\gamma]$, we obtain the homomorphism

$$\Phi := \mathbb{P} \circ \iota : K^p \rightarrow H^p; \gamma \mapsto [\gamma],$$

which we now wish to show is an isomorphism.

Injectivity: Let $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in K^p$ and suppose that $\Phi(\gamma_1) = \Phi(\gamma_2)$. In particular

$$\Phi(\gamma_1) - \Phi(\gamma_2) = [\gamma_1 - \gamma_2] = 0.$$

This implies that there exists a $\beta \in \Omega^{p-1}$ such that $\gamma_1 - \gamma_2 = d\beta$. Since γ_i are harmonic, we have that $d^*\gamma_i = 0$, thus

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \gamma_1 - \gamma_2, \gamma_1 - \gamma_2 \rangle &= \langle \gamma_1 - \gamma_2, d\beta \rangle \\ &= \langle d^*\gamma_1 - d^*\gamma_2, \beta \rangle = 0, \end{aligned}$$

i.e. $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2$ and hence the mapping Φ is injective.

Surjectivity: Let $[\omega] \in H^p$. Then by Theorem 2.30, we may write

$$\omega = d\alpha + d^*\beta + \gamma,$$

where $\alpha \in \Omega^{p-1}$, $\beta \in \Omega^{p+1}$ and $\gamma \in K^p$. But since $[\omega] \in H^p$,

$$0 = d\omega = dd^*\beta + d\gamma.$$

Since $\Delta\gamma = 0$, we have that $d\gamma = 0$ and $d^*\gamma = 0$. In particular $0 = d\omega = dd^*\beta$, and thus

$$\langle d^*\beta, d^*\beta \rangle = \langle \beta, dd^*\beta \rangle = 0 \implies d^*\beta = 0.$$

Hence $\omega = d\alpha + \gamma$ and so $[\omega] = [\gamma]$, since $d^2 = 0$. Therefore Φ is surjective, and thus also an isomorphism, as required. \square

Corollary 2.32

The discrete Laplace-de Rham operator $\Delta_p : \Omega^p \rightarrow \Omega^p$ is invertible if $H^p = \{0\}$.

Proof. To prove that Δ is invertible, we prove that it is an isomorphism if $H^p = \{0\}$.

Injectivity: Assume that $u_1, u_2 \in \Omega^p$ such that $\Delta u_1 = \Delta u_2$, in particular $\Delta(u_1 - u_2) = 0$. Then, by Proposition 2.29, it follows that $d(u_1 - u_2) = 0$ and $d^*(u_1 - u_2) = 0$, i.e. $u_1 - u_2 \in \ker d^p$, $\ker(d^{p-1})^*$. Furthermore, since $H^p = \{0\}$, by Corollary 2.31, we have that $K^p = \{0\}$, and hence by the Hodge Decomposition Theorem, Theorem 2.30

$$\Omega^p = d\Omega^{p-1} \oplus d^*\Omega^{p+1}.$$

But, note that by the Poincaré Lemma, Lemma 2.20, since $H^p = \{0\}$, all closed forms are exact, i.e. $d\Omega^{p-1} = \ker d^p$ and $d^*\Omega^{p+1} = \ker(d^{p-1})^*$, in which case, by the above, $u_1 - u_2 \in d\Omega^{p-1} \cap d^*\Omega^{p+1} = \{0\}$, i.e. $u_1 = u_2$, as required.

Surjectivity: Assume that $u \in (\text{im } \Delta)^\perp$, i.e. $\langle u, \Delta v \rangle = 0$ for all $v \in \Omega^p$. Then, by applying the definition of the differential and codifferential operators, we arrive at $\langle \Delta u, v \rangle = 0$ for all $v \in \Omega^p$, in particular $\Delta u = 0$. This implies that $u = 0$ following the same argument when proving injectivity. This concludes the proof. \square

Lemma 2.33

Assume that $H^p = \{0\}$, then the exterior derivate d and the codifferential operator d^ commutes with the inverse of the Laplace de Rham operator Δ^{-1} , i.e.*

$$d\Delta^{-1} = \Delta^{-1}d \quad \text{and} \quad d^*\Delta^{-1} = \Delta^{-1}d^*.$$

Proof. Since $H^p = \{0\}$, it follows by Corollary 2.32 that the Laplace de Rham operator

is invertible. Furthermore, by making use of Lemma 2.27, it follows that

$$d\Delta^{-1} = \Delta^{-1}\Delta d\Delta^{-1} = \Delta^{-1}d\Delta\Delta^{-1} = \Delta^{-1}d.$$

The proof for d^* is analogous. □

Important Note: From this point on, we shall slightly alter our notation in the following way. The set of differential p -forms Ω^p is currently defined as a set of homomorphisms between $C_p \rightarrow G$, where C_p denotes the set of p -chains, i.e. functions of p -cells in E_p on the defined lattice complex. For brevity, we shall now assume that the set of differential p -forms Ω^p denotes the set of functions $u : E_p \rightarrow G$, i.e. $\Omega^p := \{ u : E_p \rightarrow G \}$, where we shall implicitly consider p -chains in the definition of p -forms.

Chapter 3

Discrete Energies

In this chapter, we extend the work of Chapter 2 to define the energy of a crystal lattice when a crystal lattice under consideration is under a certain strain, using the results of [AO05]. From this point forth, unless otherwise stated, we assume that we are working in the underlying space $X = \mathbb{R}^2$ and also $G = \mathbb{R}^2$, and restrict to lattices of triangular form (in three dimensions this would correspond to the FCC lattice) due to its simple structure and accessibility. Following [GT19], we explore some of the properties of the energy functional obtained, which allow for certain simplifications in future calculations. Given these properties, we prove that due to invariance of the discrete energy under linearised rotations, grains structures are accurately modelled. We then conclude the chapter by computing energy of a grain boundary formed by two infinite parallel walls of dislocations, and show that it satisfies a Read-Shockley law, as in (1.1).

3.1 Discrete Energy of FCC Crystals in 2D

Due to its simplicity and prevalence in a number of materials, such as Copper, Nickel and Aluminium, we restrict our analysis onto triangular lattices of FCC form. More specifically, let \mathcal{L} denote a unit lattice composed of equilateral triangles, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &:= \{ n_1 a_1 + n_2 a_2 \mid n_i \in \mathbb{Z}, i = 1, 2 \}, \\ a_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad a_2 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ \sqrt{3} \end{pmatrix}, \quad a_3 = -\frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \sqrt{3} \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where a_3 has been defined for future reference. Now, denote by

- $E_0 = \mathcal{L}$ the 0-cells, i.e. the vertices of the lattice representing the atoms;
- E_1 the 1-cells, i.e. the bonds between a pair of atoms, in other words the class of oriented segments $[x, x + a_i]$, where $x, x + a_i \in E_0$;
- E_2 the 2-cells, i.e. the class of oriented faces of the lattice,

which together form the *lattice cellular complex* $X = (E_0, E_1, E_2)$. Now consider a finite portion $\Lambda \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ with prescribed boundary conditions, and let $\Lambda_p \subseteq E_p$ for $p = 0, 1, 2$ denote the p -cells in E_p that correspond with Λ , although we have to be careful with certain cells depending on the boundary conditions that we prescribe.

- In the case of *Neumann boundary conditions*, let $\Lambda_0 = \Lambda$ and Λ_p with $p = 1, 2$ be the subsets of E_p consisting of the p -cells whose set of vertices are contained in Λ ;
- In the case of *Dirichlet boundary conditions*, let Λ_p with $p = 1, 2$, be the subsets of E_p consisting of the p -cells whose set of vertices has a non-zero intersection with Λ , and we let $\Lambda_0 \supset \Lambda$ be the set of vertices of Λ_1 .
- In the case of *periodic boundary conditions*, we maintain the same cellular complex as for \mathcal{L} , but we let the p -forms of interest be those that are $\text{diam}(\Lambda)$ -periodic in the directions a_1, a_2 .

In all the above cases, we denote the cellular complex by $(\Lambda_0, \Lambda_1, \Lambda_2)$, and with a little abuse of notation, where necessary, we let Ω^p denote the set of p -forms acting on the lattice cellular complex $(\Lambda_0, \Lambda_1, \Lambda_2)$. Following [GT19], the cohomology groups of the lattice complex $(\Lambda_0, \Lambda_1, \Lambda_2)$ are given next.

Proposition 3.1

The cohomology groups associated with a section of the lattice \mathcal{L} , Λ , with Dirichlet, Neumann and periodic boundary conditions are

Dirichlet	Neumann	Periodic
$H^p = \begin{cases} \mathbb{R} & \text{if } p = 3, \\ \{0\} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$	$H^p = \begin{cases} \mathbb{R} & \text{if } p = 0, \\ \{0\} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$	$H^p = \begin{cases} \mathbb{R} & \text{if } p = 0, 3, \\ \{0\} & \text{if } p = 1, 2. \end{cases}$

In Proposition 3.2, which is a simple adaptation of Lemma 3.2 of [KK86], we now state a version of Poincaré's Lemma for FCC-lattice valued forms on Λ which shall be useful throughout this chapter. Before stating the proposition in full, we first note that a function f is deemed *lattice valued* (assuming the the lattice in consideration is \mathcal{L}) if $\text{im } f \subseteq \mathcal{L}$.

Proposition 3.2

Impose on p -forms of the cellular complex $(\Lambda_0, \Lambda_1, \Lambda_2)$ either Dirichlet or Neumann boundary conditions, in which case by the above result, $H^1 = \{0\}$. Let $q \in \Omega^2$ be a closed lattice valued 2-form with finite support. Furthermore, let \mathcal{R} denote the smallest parallelogram enclosing $\text{supp } q$. Then, there exists a constant $c > 0$ independent on the sublattice Λ , and a 1-form $n \in \Omega^1$ such that

- (i) *the form n is lattice valued;*

(ii) the form q is exact, and $dn = q$;

(iii) the support of n is contained in \mathcal{R} ;

(iv) $\max_{e \in \Lambda_1} |n(e)| \leq c\langle q, q \rangle^2$.

3.1.1 Ariza-Ortiz Model of Dislocations

Given the above lattice framework, we can continue and state the discrete energy of a sub-crystal Λ in the lattice \mathcal{L} , both in the absence and presence of dislocations using the theory developed in [AO05]. In the general sense, given a strain $\xi \in \Omega^1$ acting on the lattice, we can approximate the the total elastic energy via a harmonic expansion by

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in \Lambda_1} [\xi(e) \cdot \delta e]^2,$$

where $\delta(e) := dI(e)$, with $I \in \Omega^0$ denoting the identity function. Therefore, in the absence of dislocations and any other defects, i.e. our lattice is *perfect*, the elastic energy associated with a displacement $u : \Lambda_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \in \Omega^0$ is given by

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in \Lambda_1} [du(e) \cdot \delta e]^2,$$

that is when the strain is such that $\xi = du$.

Although, in the real world, lattices of materials tend not to be perfect in nature, and are often riddled with defects known as dislocations, which are induced by slips in the crystal structure, for example those forced by deformations of the materials. This induced imperfect structure of the lattice has a noticeable effect on the elastic energy of the material. Therefore it is important to take such defects into consideration when making calculations regarding the energy of the material. Thus let $u \in \Omega^0$ denote a deformation of the lattice and $\sigma \in \Omega^1$ account for the crystallographic slip in the lattice, i.e. where atoms are being displaced in the direction of the Burgers vector \mathbf{b} across the slip plane, where in \mathcal{L} , the Burgers vector corresponds to a_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$. To be able to make use of Proposition 3.2, we shall further assume that σ is lattice valued, which then requires the dislocation, $q = d\sigma \in \Omega^2$, formed by the pair (u, σ) to be lattice valued. To make sure that the energy associated to an edge $e \in \Lambda_1$ is independent of the orientation, we also assume that $\sigma(e) = -\sigma(-e)$, i.e. the slip is odd under orientation flip. This is inline with the assumption made on p -forms in Chapter 2.

Now, in the presence of dislocations, following [AO05], given a displacement-slip pair $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$, the total elastic energy of the lattice Λ is then given by the function $\mathcal{H} : \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, defined as

$$\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in \Lambda_1} [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2 = \frac{1}{2} \langle du - \sigma, B(du - \sigma) \rangle, \quad (3.2)$$

where $B : \Omega^1 \rightarrow \Omega^1$ is the linear function defined as follows: let $\bar{B} : E_1 \times E_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ be such that

$$\bar{B}(e, e') = \begin{cases} \delta e \otimes \delta e & \text{if } e = e', \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

Then for $e \in E_1$,

$$B\sigma(e) = \sum_{e' \in E_1} \bar{B}(e, e')\sigma(e'). \quad (3.4)$$

For brevity, we write B for the operator \bar{B} . The function B defines the type of nearest-neighbour interactions that we consider in our model. For example, if B is instead the identity operator, then B corresponds to Coulombic interactions between atoms. Throughout the thesis, to simplify calculations, we shall often simply consider the case when $\Lambda = \mathcal{L}$, in which case, we define \mathcal{H} over \mathcal{L} instead of Λ . Furthermore, when making the assumption $\Lambda = \mathcal{L}$, we need to be careful to restrict our functions in Ω^0 and Ω^1 to those that disappear sufficiently fast at infinity to make sense of the energy \mathcal{H} . In addition, we shall often also use the phrase *Ariza-Ortiz energy* to describe the function \mathcal{H} in (3.2).

Remark 3.3 (Useful Property)

We make a small remark about a property that will become of much use throughout this chapter. In particular, for $\varphi, \psi \in \Omega^1$, we have that $\langle \varphi, B\psi \rangle = \langle B\varphi, \psi \rangle$. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \varphi, B\psi \rangle &= \sum_{e, e' \in E} \varphi(e) \cdot B(e, e')\psi(e') \\ &= \sum_{e \in E} \varphi(e) \cdot (\delta e \otimes \delta e)\psi(e) \end{aligned}$$

now using the fact that $a \otimes bc = a(b \cdot c)$ for any vectors $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we have that

$$= \sum_{e \in E} (\varphi(e) \cdot \delta e)(\delta e \cdot \psi(e))$$

Figure 3.1: The shaded regions in the diagram show the two different types of faces that appear on the lattice \mathcal{L} .

and via a simple rearrangement

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{e \in E} (\psi(e) \cdot \delta e)(\delta e \cdot \varphi(e)) = \sum_{e \in E} \psi(e) \cdot (\delta e \otimes \delta e \varphi(e)) \\ &= \langle B\varphi, \psi \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

precisely as was required.

We can see that the energy \mathcal{H} is minimised when $\sigma = du$ for some pair $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$. But in this case, the slip σ does not induce a dislocation, since $d\sigma = ddu = 0$, and simply corresponds to the case of translating lattice points, which does not increase the energy of the lattice. In the problems that we'll discuss, we look at the non-trivial cases in which given a dislocation q with non-zero support, we aim to minimise \mathcal{H} over $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$ where $d\sigma = q$.

We now give some examples of dislocations and their respective slip fields. Since our lattice \mathcal{L} is triangular, there exist two types of faces in E_2 , in particular Type I and Type II type faces, these are depicted in Figure 3.1. It is easy to see that if a dislocation is purely of Type I type, then up to a rotation, there exists an equivalent dislocation of Type II associated with it (by simply flipping the lattice upside down). In the following, we shall make use of very similar notation to that used in [GT19].

Example 3.4 (Dislocation Dipole)

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let q_{dip}^n denote a dislocation dipole on faces of Type I, i.e. it is of the form

$$q_{dip}^n(f) = (\mathbf{1}_{f_0}(f) - \mathbf{1}_{f_n}(f))a_1, \quad f \in E_2 \quad (3.5)$$

where $f_j = (0, a_1, -a_3) + ja_1$ for $j \in \mathbb{Z}$.¹ For the dislocation q_{dip}^n , the 1-form, or slip field

¹We note that here we are identifying 2-cells $f \in E_2$ by as a 3-tuple of its constituent 0-cells x, y, z and represent this as $f = (x, y, z)$. We further note that $(x, y, z) + u = (x + u, y + u, z + u)$.

Figure 3.2: Depiction of the local 1-form σ_{dip}^n defined in (3.6), chosen for describing a dipolar slip configuration. Here we let f_0 denote the shaded face on the left and $f_0 + na_1$ denote the shaded face on the right, where $n = 6$.

σ_{dip}^n is such that $d\sigma_{dip}^n = q_{dip}^n$, where for $x \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{dip}^n(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } l = 2, \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ -a_1 & \text{if } l = 3, \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

See Figure 3.2 for a depiction of the slip field σ_{dip}^n when $n = 6$ with emphasis on the 1-cells on which the slip acts on. In fact, the Burgers vector of the dislocation q_{dip}^n is such that $\mathbf{b} = a_1$, although we could just as easily define it to be such that $\mathbf{b} = a_l$ for $l = 1, 2, 3$ if we simply change the value of σ_{dip}^n on edges to $\pm a_l$, as necessary.

Example 3.5 (Dislocation Dipole, Type II)

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $q_{dip}^{n,II}$ denote a dislocation dipole on faces of Type II, i.e. it is of the form

$$q_{dip}^{n,II}(f) = (\mathbf{1}_{f_0^{II}}(f) - \mathbf{1}_{f_n^{II}}(f))a_1, \quad f \in E_2.$$

where $f_j^{II} = (0, -a_3, a_2) + ja_1$ for $j \in \mathbb{Z}$. For the dislocation $q_{dip}^{n,II}$, the 1-form $\sigma_{dip}^{n,II}$ is such that $d\sigma_{dip}^{n,II} = q_{dip}^{n,II}$, where for $x \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{dip}^{n,II}(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } l = 2, \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ -a_1 & \text{if } l = 3, \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Example 3.6 (Mixed Type Dislocations)

In this example we explore dislocation dipoles which occur on faces of opposite types. Let

$$h_j := \begin{cases} (0, a_1, -a_3) + ka_1 = f_k & \text{if } j = 2k, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ (0, -a_3, a_2) + ka_1 = f_k^{II} & \text{if } j = 2k - 1, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}. \end{cases}$$

Now, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, consider the dislocation dipole q_{mix}^n defined as

$$q_{mix}^n(f) = (\mathbf{1}_{h_0}(f) - \mathbf{1}_{h_{2n+1}}(f))a_1, \quad f \in E_2$$

Then, through a simple calculation, we can show that the slip σ_{mix}^n of the form, for $x \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{mix}^n(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } l = 2, \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n+1\}, \\ -a_1 & \text{if } l = 3, \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

is such that $d\sigma_{mix}^n = q_{mix}^n$.

Example 3.7 (Two Parallel Walls of Dislocation Dipoles)

Using the notation of Example 3.4, we define a 2-form that represents two walls of dislocation dipoles. For $M, n, m \in \mathbb{N}$, let $q_{grain}^{M,n,m}$ denote this specific 2-form, i.e.

$$q_{grain}^{M,n,m}(f) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} q_{dip}^n(f - jm(a_2 - a_1)), \quad f \in E_2. \quad (3.7)$$

Then the slip $\sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}$ defined as, for $x, y \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}(x, y) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \sigma_{dip}^n(x - jm(a_2 - a_3), y - jm(a_2 - a_3)), \quad (3.8)$$

is such that $d\sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m} = q_{grain}^{M,n,m}$. Here, the values $M, n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ denote the number of dislocation dipoles, the separation between the two walls of dislocations (and hence between each dislocation dipole component) and the spacing between adjacent dislocations on the same wall, respectively.

3.1.2 Properties of the Ariza-Ortiz Energy

Unless otherwise stated, consider the Ariza-Ortiz energy \mathcal{H} given in (3.2) on the whole lattice \mathcal{L} , and recall that in this case, we assume that the displacements $u \in \Omega^0$ and slips $\sigma \in \Omega^1$ decay sufficiently fast at infinity, so that the infinite sum in (3.2) is finite. Following [GT19], we now prove that the Ariza-Ortiz energy defined on the whole lattice satisfies three particular invariances.

Proposition 3.8 (Invariances of the Ariza-Ortiz Energy)

Under the above assumptions on the discrete energy, \mathcal{H} is invariant under:

- (i) *Translations: $u \mapsto u + \kappa$ where $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is a constant vector;*
- (ii) *Gauge transformations: $(u, \sigma) \mapsto (u + v, \sigma + dv)$ where $v \in \Omega^0$ is lattice valued;*

(iii) *Linearised rotations:* $u \mapsto u + \varrho$ where $\varrho \in \Omega^0$, $\varrho(x) = Sx$ and $S \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ is a skew-symmetric matrix.

Proof. Invariance of \mathcal{H} under translations and gauge transformations follows simply by the definition of \mathcal{H} given in (3.2). It remains to prove invariance under linearised rotations. Let $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$ be a suitable displacement-slip pair and let $\varrho \in \Omega^0$ be such that $\varrho(x) = Sx$ for some skew-symmetric matrix $S \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Then

$$\mathcal{H}(u + \varrho, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in E_1} [(d(u + \varrho)(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2.$$

Now $d(u + \varrho) = du + d\varrho$, where $d\varrho(e) = S\delta e$. Since S is skew-symmetric $S = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & S_{12} \\ -S_{12} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, and so for any vector $a \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$Sa \cdot a = \begin{pmatrix} S_{12}a_2 \\ -S_{12}a_1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} = 0.$$

In particular $S\delta e \cdot \delta e = 0$, and hence we obtain the required equality, i.e.

$$\mathcal{H}(u + \varrho, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in E_1} [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2 = \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma).$$

□

Remark 3.9 (Physical Interpretations of Invariances)

We briefly remark the physical relevance of the first two invariances of the Ariza-Ortiz energy.

- (i) *Translations:* This essentially tells us that the energy of a strain due to a displacement-slip pair (u, σ) is independent on where in the lattice the displacement is performed.
- (ii) *Gauge Transformations:* This means that the energy of the lattice is independent of the location on which the displacement slip pair (u, σ) is performed and also on how we define the nearest neighbour. This gives the possibility of renumbering a given set of points on the lattice, as to make calculations simpler, with no sacrifice to energy.

Now, as a result of gauge invariance, it can be shown that the elastic energy \mathcal{H} only depends on the dislocation $q = d\sigma$ induced by the slip σ , and not directly on the pair (u, σ) . Furthermore, gauge invariance also allows us to decompose the energy into that of contributions from purely elastic interactions and also those that come as a result of the presence of the dislocation q . This result shown in Theorem 3.10.

Theorem 3.10 (Decomposition of Ariza-Ortiz Energy)

Consider the Ariza-Ortiz energy \mathcal{H} given in (3.2) with Λ under Dirichlet/Neumann boundary conditions, in which case $H^2 = \{0\}$. Furthermore, let $q \in \Omega^2$ be a lattice valued 2-form such that $dq = 0$. Then for any 0-form $u \in \Omega^0$ and any lattice valued 1-form, $\sigma \in \Omega^1$ with the property that $d\sigma = q$, the functional \mathcal{H} can be decomposed as

$$\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q),$$

where

$$\sigma_q := \arg \min_{\sigma \in \Omega^1, d\sigma = q} \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma) \quad \text{and} \quad u_q := d^* \Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q).$$

More precisely, if we consider Λ under Dirichlet boundary conditions, the minimiser σ_q is given by $\sigma_q = Gq$, where

$$G = (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^*\Delta^{-1},$$

and $A : \Omega^1 \rightarrow \Omega^1$ is the invertible operator $A := d^*Bd$ (see Theorem 3.12).

Proof. Firstly, as $d\sigma_q = d\sigma$ and since, by Lemma 2.33, d commutes with Δ^{-1}

$$d^*d\Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q) = d^*\Delta d(\sigma - \sigma_q) = 0. \quad (3.9)$$

Then by the definition of u_q and (3.9), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} du_q &= dd^*\Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q) = dd^*\Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q) + d^*d\Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q) \\ &= (dd^* + d^*d)\Delta^{-1}(\sigma - \sigma_q) \\ &= \sigma - \sigma_q, \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

where we have used the definition of the Laplacian in the last equality. Furthermore, as σ_q is the solution of a constrained minimisation problem, there exists a Lagrange parameter $\lambda \in \Omega^2$ such that σ_q satisfies the Euler-Lagrange equation $B\sigma_q = d^*\lambda$. Hence,

$$d^*B\sigma_q = d^*d^*\lambda = 0, \quad (3.11)$$

where the last equality follows by Proposition 2.25. Then, by (3.10) and (3.11), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) &= \frac{1}{2} \langle du - \sigma, B(du - \sigma) \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \langle du - \sigma + \sigma_q - \sigma_q, B(du - \sigma + \sigma_q - \sigma_q) \rangle \\ &\stackrel{(3.10)}{=} \frac{1}{2} \langle du - du_q - \sigma_q, B(du - du_q - \sigma_q) \rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle d(u - u_q), B(d(u - u_q) - \sigma_q) \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_q, B(d(u - u_q) - \sigma_q) \rangle \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle d(u - u_q), Bd(u - u_q) \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d(u - u_q), B\sigma_q \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_q, Bd(u - u_q) \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_q, B\sigma_q \rangle \\
&= \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) - \frac{1}{2} \langle d(u - u_q), B\sigma_q \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_q, Bd(u - u_q) \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

then by Remark 3.3

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) - \langle d(u - u_q), B\sigma_q \rangle \\
&= \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) - \langle u - u_q, d^* B\sigma_q \rangle \\
&\stackrel{(3.11)}{=} \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q),
\end{aligned}$$

as required. Now to derive the solution operator G for σ_q , we first observe that by the Hodge Decomposition Theorem, Theorem 2.30,

$$\Omega^1 = d\Omega^0 \oplus d^*\Omega^2 = \ker d^1 \oplus \ker(d^0)^*.$$

Thus we can decompose the minimiser σ_q , in terms of $\varphi \in \ker d^1$ and $\psi \in \ker(d^0)^*$, as

$$\sigma_q = \varphi + \psi.$$

Since $d\sigma_q = q$ and $d\varphi = 0$, we find that

$$q = d\sigma_q = d\varphi + d\psi = d\psi.$$

Then, since $d^*\psi = 0$, using the fact that d^* commutes with Δ^{-1} , see Lemma 2.33, we get

$$d^*\Delta^{-1}q = d^*\Delta^{-1}d\psi = \Delta^{-1}d^*d\psi = \Delta^{-1}(d^*d + dd^*)\psi = \psi. \quad (3.12)$$

Furthermore, by the boundary conditions on Λ , since $H^2 = \{0\}$ and also since $d\varphi = 0$, by Proposition 3.2, there exists a $u_0 \in \Omega^0$ such that $du_0 = \varphi$. Hence by (3.12)

$$\sigma_q = du_0 + d^*\Delta^{-1}q. \quad (3.13)$$

Using the fact that $d^*B\sigma_q = 0$ by (3.11), it follows that

$$d^*B(d^*\Delta^{-1}q + du_0) = d^*B\sigma_q = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

Given the definition of $A = d^*Bd$, by (3.14)

$$u_0 = -A^{-1}d^*Bd^*\Delta^{-1}q,$$

and so by (3.13)

$$\sigma_q = du_0 + d^* \Delta^{-1} q = (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^* \Delta^{-1} q,$$

which is precisely what was required. \square

As a result of the additive decomposition of the Ariza-Ortiz energy, the following consequence follows immediately.

Corollary 3.11

Assuming the conditions of Theorem 3.10, we have that

$$\mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) = \min_{u \in \Omega^0} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma),$$

and hence, in particular

$$\min_{\substack{(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \\ d\sigma = q}} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle q, G^* B G q \rangle, \quad (3.15)$$

i.e. that the energy only depends on the dislocation q .

Proof. Let σ be as in Theorem 3.10. Then, we have that

$$\min_{u \in \Omega^0} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \min_{u \in \Omega^0} \mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) + \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) = \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q),$$

since choosing $u = u_q$ implies $\mathcal{H}(u - u_q, 0) = 0$. Then, the second part of the proof follows by simply taking the minimum of the above equality over all admissible slips, which yields

$$\min_{u \in \Omega^0} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \mathcal{H}(0, \sigma_q) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_q, B \sigma_q \rangle$$

and since by Theorem 3.10, $\sigma_q = Gq$, it follows that

$$= \frac{1}{2} \langle q, G^* B G q \rangle,$$

as required. \square

Theorem 3.12 (Invertibility of $A = d^* B d$)

Let $A := d^ B d : \Omega^0 \rightarrow \Omega^0$ where B is defined as in the definition of (3.2). Then the operator A is invertible.*

Proof. This result follows via an adaptation of Appendix B.1 from [GT19]. \square

We have shown above that the minimum of the Ariza-Ortiz energy under the set of admissible displacement-slip pairs depends only on the dislocation part, and hence has a

representation in terms of only a dislocation $q \in \Omega^2$. Now say that we represent $q = d\varphi$ for some $\varphi \in \Omega^1$, then we can indeed usefully represent the Ariza-Ortiz energy as a function of φ instead.

Corollary 3.13 (Slip Representation of the Ariza-Ortiz Energy)

Assume the conditions of Theorem 3.10 and let $\varphi \in \Omega^1$ be such that $d\varphi = q$. Then

$$\min_{(u,\sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^* B\varphi, A^{-1} d^* B\varphi \rangle.$$

Proof. By Corollary 3.11, we indeed have that

$$\min_{(u,\sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle q, G^* B G q \rangle,$$

where $G = (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^*\Delta^{-1}$, $G^* = \Delta^{-1}d(1 - BdA^{-1}d^*)$ and $A = d^*Bd$. By the hypothesis, we know that $d\varphi = q$, and therefore due to gauge invariance of the Ariza-Ortiz energy

$$\min_{(u,\sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \min_{u \in \Omega^0} \mathcal{H}(u, \varphi).$$

Now, expanding via the definition of G yields

$$\begin{aligned} Gq &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^*\Delta^{-1}q \\ &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^*\Delta^{-1}d\varphi \end{aligned}$$

and by the fact that the exterior derivative commutes with the inverse Laplacian, Lemma 2.33, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)d^*d\Delta^{-1}\varphi \\ &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)(d^*d + dd^*)\Delta^{-1}\varphi - (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)dd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi \\ &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi - (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)dd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi \\ &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi - dd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi + dA^{-1}d^*Bdd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi \end{aligned}$$

and then by the definition of A ,

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi - dd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi + dd^*\Delta^{-1}\varphi \\ &= (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\min_{(u,\sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle q, G^* B G q \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \langle Gq, B G q \rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi, B(1 - dA^{-1}d^*B)\varphi \rangle \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, BdA^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle dA^{-1}d^*B\varphi, B\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \langle dA^{-1}d^*B\varphi, BdA^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle
\end{aligned}$$

then by Remark 3.3 and by the fact that the displacement $u \in \Omega^0$ that minimises $\mathcal{H}(u, \varphi)$ satisfies $Au = d^*B\varphi$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle B\varphi, dA^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle A^{-1}d^*B\varphi, d^*B\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \langle A^{-1}d^*B\varphi, d^*BdA^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^*B\varphi, A^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle A^{-1}d^*B\varphi, d^*B\varphi \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \langle A^{-1}d^*B\varphi, d^*B\varphi \rangle \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^*B\varphi, A^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle.
\end{aligned}$$

In particular

$$\min_{(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \varphi, B\varphi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^*B\varphi, A^{-1}d^*B\varphi \rangle,$$

as required. □

3.2 The Energy of Grains and Read-Shockley Law

Having established properties of the Ariza-Ortiz energy, we move to the main topic of this chapter. When considering models for crystal mechanics, it is important to ask how much of the real world the model under consideration mimics. As discussed in the introduction, the presence of dislocations in materials can lead to the formation of structures in materials known as *grains*, where each grain represents its own sublattice. Grains form as a result of a series of dislocations isolating a section of a lattice and distorting it. Often, materials form a number of grains, due to the presence of dislocations, where adjacent grains are separated by the *grain boundaries*. Given their prevalence in the real world, it would not make much sense to study a model which does not take such structures into account, and therefore a question arises on whether the Ariza-Ortiz model considered accurately models the energy of grains. One initial indication that the Ariza-Ortiz model does allow for the existence of grains is by the fact that it is invariant under linearised rotations. Since grains are essentially sublattices that are oriented off the initial axis, grains can be represented as linearised rotations of sections of the original lattice.

To check the accuracy of the Ariza-Ortiz model for grains, first let $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ denote the location of a grain, which we assume to be connected, bounded. In this section, we first define what it means for a displacement-slip pair to be *gauge equivalent* to another displacement-slip pair.

Definition 3.14 (Gauge Equivalence)

A displacement-slip pair $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$ is said to be *gauge equivalent* to another displacement-slip pair $(u', \sigma') \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1$ if

$$(u', \sigma') = (u' + v, \sigma + dv),$$

for some lattice valued 0-form $v \in \Omega^0$.

Now, as in [GT19], we define what it means for a displacement-slip pair to support a perfect grain.

Definition 3.15

Let $S \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ denote a skew-symmetric matrix. We say that a displacement field $u \in \Omega^0$ and a lattice valued slip field $\sigma \in \Omega^1$ *supports a perfect grain \mathcal{G} with orientation S* if they are *gauge equivalent* to another displacement-slip pair (u', σ') such that

$$du'(e) = \begin{cases} S\delta e & \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G}, \\ 0 & \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G}^c, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\sigma'(e) = 0 \quad \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G} \quad \text{or} \quad e \in \mathcal{G}^c,$$

with the convention that $e = [x, x'] \in \mathcal{G}$ if $\{x, x'\} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$, and noting that $\delta e = dI(e)$.

Note that in Definition 3.15, no conditions on edges $e = [x, y]$ that connect the inside and outside of the grain \mathcal{G} , i.e. such that $x \in \mathcal{G}$ and $y \in \mathcal{G}^c$ (or vice versa) have been stated. We shall consider these edges separately, and denote by $\partial\mathcal{G}$ the set of such edges, i.e.

$$\partial\mathcal{G} := \{ e \in E_1 \mid e = [x, y], \{x, y\} \cap \mathcal{G} \neq \emptyset \text{ and } \{x, y\} \cap \mathcal{G}^c \neq \emptyset \}.$$

Furthermore, for any set $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, denote by $E_1(\mathcal{V}) := \{ e \in E_1 \mid e \in \mathcal{V} \}$ the 1-cells that connect the lattice points in \mathcal{V} . For a constant $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$, consider, for the purposes of the next result, a piecewise affine map $u_S : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ such that

$$u_S(x) := \begin{cases} Sx + \tau & \text{if } x \in \mathcal{G}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In the next result, we shall prove a 2D analogue of Theorem 3.2 from [GT19] which states the result for 3D lattices, i.e. that grains are indeed modelled accurately via the Ariza-Ortiz model.

Theorem 3.16

Let $S \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ be a skew-symmetric matrix and $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ denote a bounded and connected set, representing a grain. Then

$$\min_{(u, \sigma) \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) \leq \frac{9}{2} |\partial \mathcal{G}|, \quad (3.16)$$

where

$$\mathcal{A} := \left\{ (u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \mid \text{im } \sigma \subseteq \mathcal{L} \text{ and } (u, \sigma) \text{ supports a perfect grain } \mathcal{G} \text{ with orientation } S \right\}.$$

Proof. First, let $u = u_S$ with $\tau = 0$. We begin by decomposing the skew-symmetric matrix S into simple slips. We first note that

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & S_{12} \\ -S_{12} & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

for $S_{12} \in \mathbb{R}$. Now, under the given lattice structure, the possible slip directions are a_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Furthermore, the unit normals to the slip planes induced by a_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$ are

$$n_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad n_2 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad n_3 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{3} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

With the slip systems (s_i, n_i) for $i = 1, 2, 3$, we can in fact write

$$S = \frac{S_{12}}{3} [a_1 \otimes n_1 - a_2 \otimes n_2 - a_3 \otimes n_3] = \sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i a_i \otimes n_i,$$

where $\xi_1 = \frac{S_{12}}{3}$ and $\xi_2 = \xi_3 = -\frac{S_{12}}{3}$. Now define a lattice valued slip $\sigma \in \Omega^1$ with support on $\partial \mathcal{G}$, which is defined as follows: for $e \in E_1$,

$$\sigma(e) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i [\xi_i x \cdot n_i] & \text{if } e = [x, y] \in \partial \mathcal{G} \text{ with } x \in \mathcal{G} \text{ and } y \in \mathcal{G}^c, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Now, we may decompose the set of edges of the lattice with respect to the edges on the grain boundary, i.e. as

$$E_1 = E_1(\mathcal{G}) \cup \partial \mathcal{G} \cup E_1(\mathcal{G}^c).$$

Given this decomposition, we may also decompose the Ariza-Ortiz energy with respect to these edges, i.e.

$$\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{e \in E_1(\mathcal{G})} + \sum_{e \in \partial\mathcal{G}} + \sum_{e \in E_1(\mathcal{G}^c)} \right) [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2.$$

Since u and σ are only defined on \mathcal{G} and $\partial\mathcal{G}$, it is clear that the sum with respect to $E_1(\mathcal{G}^c)$ is zero. Furthermore, since σ only has support on $\partial\mathcal{G}$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{e \in E_1(\mathcal{G})} [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2 &= \sum_{e \in E_1(\mathcal{G})} [du(e) \cdot \delta e]^2 \\ &= \sum_{e \in E_1(\mathcal{G})} [S\delta e \cdot \delta e]^2 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows since $S\delta e \cdot \delta e = 0$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in \partial\mathcal{G}} [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} [(u(x) - \sigma(x, y)) \cdot (x - y)]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left[\left(Sx - \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i [\xi_i x \cdot n_i] \right) \cdot (x - y) \right]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i a_i \otimes n_i x - \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i [\xi_i x \cdot n_i] \right) \cdot (x - y) \right]^2, \end{aligned}$$

and now using the fact that $a \otimes bc = a(b \cdot c)$ for any vectors $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i a_i x \cdot n_i - \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i [\xi_i x \cdot n_i] \right) \cdot (x - y) \right]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^3 (\xi_i x \cdot n_i - [\xi_i x \cdot n_i]) a_i \cdot (x - y) \right]^2 \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left| \sum_{i=1}^3 (\xi_i x \cdot n_i - [\xi_i x \cdot n_i]) a_i \right|^2 |x - y|^2, \end{aligned}$$

and since $|x - y| = 1$ and $|a_i| = 1$, it follows that

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{(x,y) \in \partial\mathcal{G} \\ x \in \mathcal{G}, y \in \mathcal{G}^c}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^3 (\xi_i x \cdot n_i - [\xi_i x \cdot n_i]) \right]^2.$$

Now because $0 \leq \xi_i x \cdot n_i - \lfloor \xi_i x \cdot n_i \rfloor \leq 1$, we have that $0 \leq \sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i x \cdot n_i - \lfloor \xi_i x \cdot n_i \rfloor \leq 3$, and thus $[\sum_{i=1}^3 \xi_i x \cdot n_i - \lfloor \xi_i x \cdot n_i \rfloor]^2 \leq 9$. Therefore

$$\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) \leq \frac{9}{2} |\partial \mathcal{G}|,$$

which gives the required bound. □

Equation (3.16) shows that the energy of grain scales like the size of the boundary. Since the coefficient of the size of the boundary (3.16) has been deduced via example, it is likely that this bound can be improved, i.e. we can find another constant $0 < C \leq \frac{9}{2}$ such that $\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) \leq C |\partial \mathcal{G}|$. The sharpness of the bound on the energy of a grain can be further deduced by proving that there exists a constant $D > 0$ such that $\mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) \geq D |\partial \mathcal{G}|$ for $(u, \sigma) \in \mathcal{A}$. Heuristically speaking, it is possible to find such a constant D by the following procedure. If we let $(u, \sigma) \in \mathcal{A}$, then by definition, there exists a gauge equivalent pair $(u', \sigma') \in \mathcal{A}$ such that

$$du'(e) = \begin{cases} S \delta e & \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G}, \\ 0 & \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G}^c, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\sigma'(e) = 0 \quad \text{if } e \in \mathcal{G} \quad \text{or} \quad e \in \mathcal{G}^c.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) &= \mathcal{H}(u', \sigma') = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in \partial \mathcal{G}} [(du'(e) - \sigma'(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2 \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} |\partial \mathcal{G}| \min_{e \in \partial \mathcal{G}} [(du'(e) - \sigma'(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2. \end{aligned}$$

Showing that $\min_{e \in \partial \mathcal{G}} [(du'(e) - \sigma'(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2$ is bounded below by a constant D would complete the proof and give us a range of values for the proportionality constant between the energy of a grain and the size of its boundary.

Furthermore, Theorem 3.16 shows that the energy of grains scales like the size of the boundary. This is in parallel with what we observe in the real world. As the boundary of a grain grows, the number of dislocations and hence points that stress the lattice increase, which as a result increases the elastic energy of the lattice.

3.2.1 Explicit Computation of the Energy of a Grain Boundary

In this subsection, we compute the energy of a grain produced by the presence of a dipole (a pair of dislocations of opposite *charges*) and of two walls of dislocations with opposite charges. This set up is of particular interest since it allows for an introductory example into the behaviour of the Ariza-Ortiz energy before endeavouring to calculating energies for more complicated scenarios. Furthermore, two parallel walls of dislocations with opposite charges corresponds to a grain supported in the region between two walls, very much like that of the set up of a capacitor where each wall of dislocations mimics a capacitor plate. For the sake of simplicity, we perform computations assuming that $\Lambda = \mathcal{L}$ and that forms on this space vanish sufficiently fast at infinity to make sense of the Ariza-Ortiz energy, also noting that the case of a finite volume, i.e. when $\Lambda \subset \mathcal{L}$, can be easily considered by the appropriate use of Dirichlet, Neumann or periodic boundary conditions.

To perform some of these explicit calculations, we shall define discrete version of the Fourier transform as follows.

Definition 3.17 (Fourier Transform of Discrete Forms)

Let $v \in \Omega^0$ and $\varphi \in \Omega^1$ represent forms. Then, for $x \in \mathcal{L}$, their respective Fourier transform is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} v(x) &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \hat{v}(k) e^{-ik \cdot x} \, dk, \\ \varphi(x, x + a_l) &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \hat{\varphi}(k, l) e^{-ik \cdot x} \, dk, \quad l = 1, 2, 3, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\mathcal{B} := \{ k \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid k \cdot a_l \in [0, 2\pi), \, l = 1, 2 \},$$

denotes the first *Brillouin zone*, and $|\mathcal{B}| = \frac{8\pi^2}{\sqrt{3}}$ denotes its area. In particular, we may write, for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{v}(k) &:= \sum_{x \in E_0} v(x) e^{ik \cdot x}, \\ \hat{\varphi}(k, l) &= \sum_{e \in E_1} \varphi(x, x + a_l) e^{ik \cdot x}, \quad l = 1, 2, 3. \end{aligned}$$

Under this Fourier transform, we may also represent the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ of 0-forms in an alternate form given below.

Definition 3.18

We note that for $f, g \in \Omega^0$, the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ may also be evaluated as

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{\hat{f}(k)} \cdot \hat{g}(k) \, dk,$$

where $\overline{\hat{f}(k)}$ denotes the complex conjugate of $\hat{f}(k)$, i.e. $\overline{\hat{f}(k)} = \hat{f}(-k)$.

Furthermore, the Fourier transform also allows for the following type of behaviour.

Lemma 3.19

For an invertible operator $\mathcal{T} : \Omega^0 \rightarrow \Omega^0$ and for a function $f \in \Omega^0$, we have that

$$\widehat{\mathcal{T}^{-1}f}(k) = \hat{\mathcal{T}}^{-1}(k)\hat{f}(k), \quad k \in \mathbb{R}^2$$

where $\hat{\mathcal{T}}$ denotes the Fourier symbol of the operator \mathcal{T} , i.e. $\hat{\mathcal{T}}$ is defined such that $\widehat{\mathcal{T}f} = \hat{\mathcal{T}}\hat{f}$.

Proof. Since \mathcal{T} is invertible, we have that $id_{\Omega^0} = \mathcal{T}\mathcal{T}^{-1}$, therefore

$$\hat{f} = \widehat{\mathcal{T}\mathcal{T}^{-1}f} = \hat{\mathcal{T}}\widehat{\mathcal{T}^{-1}f},$$

and hence $\widehat{\mathcal{T}^{-1}f} = \hat{\mathcal{T}}^{-1}\hat{f}$, as required. □

Energy from a Dislocation Dipole

We first deduce the Ariza-Ortiz energy for a dislocation dipole, which has been formed by a pair of dislocations with opposite charges, i.e. opposite Burger's vectors separated by a distance n , exactly as in Example 3.4, i.e.

$$q_{dip}^n(f) := (\mathbf{1}_{f_0}(f) - \mathbf{1}_{f_n}(f)) a_1, \quad f \in E_2,$$

where we recall that $f_j = (0, a_1, -a_3) + ja_1$ for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

Theorem 3.20

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $E_{dip}(n)$ denote the Ariza-Ortiz energy under a dislocation dipole q_{dip}^n , i.e.

$$E_{dip}(n) := \min_{\substack{(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \\ d\sigma = q_{dip}^n}} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma).$$

Then, $E_{dip}(n)$ has the following asymptotic representation

$$E_{dip}(n) = \frac{\log n}{2\pi\sqrt{3}} + \mathcal{O}(1) \quad \text{for } n \gg 1.$$

Proof. Firstly, by Corollary 3.13, since for q_{dip}^n , we have that $d\sigma_{dip}^n = q_{dip}^n$, where σ_{dip}^n is defined as in Example 3.4, it follows that

$$E_{dip}(n) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \sigma_{dip}^n, B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle. \quad (3.17)$$

Having obtained a simpler to work with representation of the energy of a dipole, we can begin to compute the terms in the inner products explicitly. It is easy to show that for $x \in \mathcal{L}$ and $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$

$$B\sigma_{dip}^n(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2}a_2 & \text{if } l = 2 \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ +\frac{1}{2}a_3 & \text{if } l = 3 \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Using this equality, we can then see that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \sigma_{dip}^n, B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle &= \sum_{e \in E_1} \sigma_{dip}^n(e) \cdot B\sigma_{dip}^n(e) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_{dip}^n(ja_1, ja_1 + a_2) \cdot B\sigma_{dip}^n(ja_1, ja_1 + a_2) + \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_{dip}^n(ja_1 - a_3, ja_1 - a_3 + a_2) \cdot B\sigma_{dip}^n(ja_1 - a_3, ja_1 - a_3 + a_2) \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n a_1 \cdot (a_2 + a_3) = \frac{n}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

which establishes the first term on the right hand side of (3.17). Now by Definition 3.18 and Lemma 3.19, the second term on the right hand side of (3.17) may be written in Fourier form

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{\widehat{d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k)} \cdot \widehat{A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k) dk,$$

where we have used Lemma 3.19. We represent this inner product in Fourier form due to the presence of the operator A^{-1} in the inner product, and an explicit form of this is unknown. Now, since for any $\varphi \in \Omega^1$ we have that

$$d^* \varphi(x) = \sum_{l=1}^3 (\varphi(x - a_l, x) - \varphi(x, x + a_l)), \quad x \in \mathcal{L}, \quad (3.18)$$

and directly applying the definition of the Fourier transform, Definition 3.17, we get that

$$= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left[\sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \widehat{\varphi}(k, l) \right] e^{-ik \cdot x} dk.$$

Applying Definition 3.17 again, we find that for any 1-form $\varphi \in \Omega^1$,

$$\widehat{d^* \varphi}(k) = \sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \hat{\varphi}(k, l).$$

Using the above result with $\varphi = B\sigma_{dip}^n$, we obtain that for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\widehat{d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k) = \sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) B\hat{\sigma}_{dip}^n(k, l).$$

Since for $(k, l) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \times \{1, 2, 3\}$

$$\widehat{B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k, l) = \sum_{x \in E_1} B\sigma(x, x + a_l) e^{ik \cdot x},$$

via a simple expansion, we obtain that for $(k, l) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \times \{1, 2, 3\}$

$$\widehat{B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k, l) = \begin{cases} -\frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} a_2 & \text{if } l = 2, \\ \frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} e^{-ik \cdot a_3} a_3 & \text{if } l = 3, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.19)$$

In particular, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k) &= \sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \widehat{B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k, l) \\ &= \left[-\frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \right] \left[\frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right] [(e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

Therefore, noting that $\hat{A}(k)$ denotes the Fourier symbol of the operator A

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{\widehat{d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k)} \cdot \hat{A}^{-1}(k) \widehat{d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n}(k) \, dk \\ &= \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left| \frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right|^2 F(k) \, dk, \end{aligned}$$

where, for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$F(k) := [(e^{-ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{ik \cdot a_3})a_3] \hat{A}^{-1}(k) [(e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3]. \quad (3.21)$$

Since $|e^{i\gamma} - 1|^2 = 2(1 - \cos(\gamma))$ for any $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, it follows that

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{dip}^n \rangle = \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk.$$

Since $A = d^* B d$, it follows that for any $u \in \Omega^0$,

$$Au(x) = \sum (a_l \otimes a_l)(2u(x) - u(x + a_l) - u(x - a_l)),$$

and, as before, applying Definition 3.17, we get that

$$= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left[2 \sum_{l=1}^3 (a_l \otimes a_l)(1 - \cos(k \cdot a_l)) \hat{u}(k) \right] e^{-ik \cdot x} dk.$$

In particular, we have that

$$\widehat{Au}(k) = 2 \sum_{l=1}^3 (a_l \otimes a_l)(1 - \cos(k \cdot a_l)) \hat{u}(k) = \hat{A}(k) \hat{u}(k),$$

where

$$\hat{A}(k) = 2 \sum_{l=1}^3 (a_l \otimes a_l)(1 - \cos(k \cdot a_l)) \quad k \in \mathbb{R}^2.$$

Then, writing $\hat{A}(k)$ out in full we can easily compute that for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\det \hat{A}(k) = 3 \left(\cos\left(\frac{k_1}{2}\right) - \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}\right) \right)^2 + 6 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{k_1}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}\right) \right) (1 - \cos(k_1)),$$

where $\det \hat{A}(k) \geq 0$ for all $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$. It is easy to see that $\det \hat{A}(k) = 0$ if and only if $k \in \mathcal{L}^*$, where \mathcal{L}^* is the reciprocal lattice of \mathcal{L} , i.e.

$$\mathcal{L}^* = \{ n_1 m_1 + n_2 m_2 \mid n_i \in \mathbb{Z}, i = 1, 2, \text{ and } m_i \cdot a_j = 2\pi \delta_{ij} \}.$$

Therefore, $F(k)$ is only defined when $k \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \mathcal{L}^*$, since the inverse of \hat{A} only makes sense on this domain. Letting $\Phi_k := k \otimes k / |k|^2$ denote the scaled projection in the direction $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$ where $|k|^2 = k_1^2 + k_2^2$, by using the Taylor expansion of \cos about the singularity $k = 0$ of \hat{A} yields

$$\hat{A}(k) = 2 \sum_{l=1}^3 \Pi_l (1 - \cos(k \cdot a_l)) = \sum_{l=1}^3 (k \cdot a_l)^2 \Pi_l + \mathcal{O}(|k|^4).$$

Letting $\mathbb{I} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ denote the identity matrix and expanding the above sum gives us

$$= \frac{3}{8} |k|^2 (\mathbb{I} + 2\Phi_k) + \mathcal{O}(|k|^4),$$

so that in particular, about the singularity $k = 0$

$$\hat{A}^{-1}(k) = \frac{8}{9|k|^2}(3\mathbb{I} - 2\Phi_k)(1 + \mathcal{O}(|k|^2)). \quad (3.22)$$

Now by the form of \hat{A}^{-1} given above, we can see that in the vicinity of k away from the singularity of \hat{A} at zero, $F(k)$ even, uniformly bounded on \mathcal{B} and analytic in k . Furthermore, inputting (3.22) into the definition of F , about $k = 0$,

$$F(k) = 2 - \frac{16}{3} \frac{k_1^2 k_2^2}{|k|^4} + \mathcal{O}(|k|^2).$$

To extract the dominant contributions from the second term on the right hand side of (3.17), it is useful to rewrite F in the form

$$F(k) = F((0, k_2)) + [F(k) - F((0, k_2))],$$

with $F((0, k_2)) = 2$ by part (ii) of Lemma 3.24, and check the contributions from each term separately, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d^* B \sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{dip}^n \rangle &= \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F((0, k_2)) \, dk \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} [F(k) - F((0, k_2))] \, dk. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F((0, k_2)) \, dk &= \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \, dk \\ &= \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{B}|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{\frac{k_1}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{3}}} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \, dk_2 \, dk_1 \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \, dk_1 \end{aligned}$$

and for any small $\varepsilon > 0$, since $\frac{1}{1 - \cos(u)}$ is bounded in the set $(-\pi, \pi) \setminus (-\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_0^\varepsilon \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \, dk_1 \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{2\pi - \varepsilon}^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \, dk_1 + \mathcal{O}(1), \end{aligned}$$

and then using the 2π -periodicity of the cosine function

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\varepsilon}^{\varepsilon} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{k_1^2} dk_1 + \mathcal{O}(1) = \frac{n}{2} + \mathcal{O}(1), \quad (3.23)$$

where the last equality is obtained via a computation, and also the remainder $\mathcal{O}(1)$ is uniformly bounded as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, applying a similar technique to the one above, for any small $\varepsilon > 0$ (expanding $F(k)$ around $k = 0$)

$$\frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} [F(k) - F((0, k_2))] dk = \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{[-\varepsilon, \varepsilon]^2} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{k_1^2/2} \left[\frac{16 k_1^2 k_2^2}{3 |k|^4} \right] dk + \mathcal{O}(1)$$

where, again, the remainder term $\mathcal{O}(1)$ is uniformly bounded as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then through an explicit computation of the integral above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{1}{\pi^2 \sqrt{3}} \int_{[-\varepsilon, \varepsilon]^2} \frac{k_2^2 (1 - \cos(k_1 n))}{|k|^4} dk + \mathcal{O}(1) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\pi \sqrt{3}} \int_0^{\varepsilon} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{k_1} dk_1 + \mathcal{O}(1) \\ &= -\frac{\log n}{\pi \sqrt{3}} + \mathcal{O}(1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in particular

$$\langle d^* B \sigma_{dip}^n, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{dip}^n \rangle = \frac{n}{2} - \frac{\log n}{\pi \sqrt{3}} + \mathcal{O}(1).$$

Putting the above results together, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} E_{dip}(n) &= \frac{n}{4} - \frac{n}{4} + \frac{\log n}{2\pi \sqrt{3}} + \mathcal{O}(1) \\ &= \frac{\log n}{2\pi \sqrt{3}} + \mathcal{O}(1), \end{aligned}$$

precisely as was required. \square

Energy from a Pair of Infinite Grain Boundaries

We now perform energy calculations of a pair of parallel dislocation walls, which in the limit as the number of dislocations goes to infinity, form a pair of infinite grain boundaries, i.e. dislocations formed by 2-form presented in Example 3.7,

$$q_{grain}^{M,n,m}(f) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} q_{dip}^n(f - jm(a_2 - a_3)).$$

One can see that in the limit as $M \rightarrow \infty$, the distribution of $q_{grain}^{M,n,m}$ represents that of two infinite walls of dislocations separated by a distance n with charge density $1/m$ along each wall. What we shall show below is that in the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, i.e for large grain, the Ariza-Ortiz energy of the lattice under these dislocations (i.e. the energy of the grain) satisfies the Read-Shockley law asymptotically as the angle of rotation of the grain with respect to the background lattice, $\theta = \frac{1}{m}$, tends to zero. Before beginning with the proof of the main theorem of this chapter, we first prove a result that shall become useful in Theorem 3.22.

Lemma 3.21

For $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$, we define a sequence of functions $(K_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ as

$$K_n(x) := \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n(1 - \cos(x))}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N},$$

Then, $K_n \rightarrow 2\pi\delta(0)$ in the sense of distributions as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the well known Dirac delta distribution.

Proof. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the function K_n is in fact the n th Fejér kernel. Since a sequence of Fejér kernels forms a family of good kernels, it follows that for any function $f \in L^1([-\pi, \pi]) \cap L^\infty([-\pi, \pi])$ that is continuous at 0, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} K_n(x) f(x) dx = 2\pi f(0),$$

which is precisely as was required. □

Theorem 3.22

For $n, m, M \in \mathbb{N}$, let $E_{grain}(n, m)$ denote the Ariza-Ortiz energy density of a grain boundary per unit length, i.e.

$$E_{grain}(n, m) := \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}mM} \min_{\substack{(u, \sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \\ d\sigma = q_{grain}^{M,n,m}}} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma).$$

Then, $E_{grain}(n, m)$ has the following asymptotic representation

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{grain}(n, m) = \frac{\log m}{6\pi m} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right), \quad \text{for } m \gg 1. \quad (3.24)$$

Proof. We begin the proof exactly as we did for Theorem 3.20, that is by representing $E_{grain}(n, m)$ in terms of the slip $\sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}$ which is defined as

$$\sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}(x, x') := \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \sigma_{dip}^n(x + mj(a_2 - a_3), x' + mj(a_2 - a_3)).$$

In particular, by Corollary 3.13, we have that

$$\frac{1}{M} \min_{\substack{(u,\sigma) \in \Omega^0 \times \Omega^1 \\ d\sigma = q_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}}} \mathcal{H}(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2M} \langle \sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}, B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} \rangle - \frac{1}{2M} \langle d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} \rangle.$$

Now, for $x \in \mathcal{L}$ and $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$

$$B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x, x + a_l) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(x + mj(a_2 - a_3), x + a_l + mj(a_2 - a_3)).$$

Therefore, by (3.18) and by the definition of $\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}$, it follows that for $x \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\begin{aligned} d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x) &= \sum_{l=1}^3 (-B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x, x + a_l) + B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x - a_l, x)) \\ &= \sum_{l=1}^3 \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} (-B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(y, y + a_l) + B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(z, z + a_l)), \end{aligned}$$

where $y = x + mj(a_2 - a_3)$, $z = x - a_l + mj(a_2 - a_3)$. Then applying the definition of the Fourier transform, see Definition 3.17, yields

$$\begin{aligned} d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x) &= \sum_{l=1}^3 \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \left[\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \widehat{B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n}(k, l) (e^{-ik \cdot z} - e^{-ik \cdot y}) \, dk \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left[\sum_{l=1}^3 \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} e^{-imjk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \widehat{B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n}(k, l) \right] e^{-ik \cdot x} \, dk \end{aligned}$$

and evaluating the sum with index j yields

$$= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left[\frac{e^{-iMmk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1}{e^{-imk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1} \sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \widehat{B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n}(k, l) \right] e^{-ik \cdot x} \, dk,$$

thus, using (3.19), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}}(k) &= \frac{e^{-iMmk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1}{e^{-imk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1} \sum_{l=1}^3 (e^{ik \cdot a_l} - 1) \widehat{B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n}(k, l) \\ &= \left[-\frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \right] \left[\frac{e^{-iMmk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1}{e^{-imk \cdot (a_2 - a_3)} - 1} \right] \left[\frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right] P(k) \end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

where $P(k) = [(e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3]$. Therefore, noting that $\hat{A}(k)$ denotes the Fourier symbol of the operator A

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} \rangle = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \widehat{d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}}(k) \cdot \hat{A}^{-1}(k) \widehat{d^* B\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}}(k) \, dk$$

$$= \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left| \frac{e^{-iMm\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1}{e^{-im\sqrt{k_2}} - 1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right|^2 F(k) \, dk,$$

where, for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $F(k)$ is defined as in (3.21). Since $|e^{i\gamma} - 1|^2 = 2(1 - \cos(\gamma))$ for any $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, it follows that

$$\langle d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m} \rangle = \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} F(k) \, dk.$$

Now, we can expand the integral over \mathcal{B} into that over its three components. This then yields the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{M} \langle d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m} \rangle &= \frac{1}{4M|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} F(k) \, dk \\ &= \frac{1}{4M|\mathcal{B}|} \left[\int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_0^{k_2\sqrt{3}} + \int_{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_0^{2\pi} + \int_{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{6\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_{k_2\sqrt{3}-4\pi}^{2\pi} \right] \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} F(k) \, dk. \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

$$(3.27)$$

To simplify the notation, let

$$\begin{aligned} G(k_2) &:= \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk_1 \\ G_1(k_2) &:= \int_0^{k_2\sqrt{3}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk_1 \\ G_3(k_2) &:= \int_{k_2\sqrt{3}-4\pi}^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk_1 \end{aligned}$$

Second Term: We first evaluate the second pair of integrals on the right hand side of (3.26), more precisely

$$\frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} G(k_2) \, dk_2. \quad (3.28)$$

Changing variables via $u = m\sqrt{3}k_2$ in (3.28), we get

$$\frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} G(k_2) \, dk_2 = \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{2\pi m}^{4\pi m} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \, du.$$

Then decomposing the integral further into intervals of length 2π about each of the singularity points of $\frac{1}{1-\cos(u)}$ yields

$$= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \left[\int_{2\pi m}^{2\pi m+\pi} + \sum_{j=m+1}^{2m-1} \int_{2\pi j-\pi}^{2\pi j+\pi} + \int_{4\pi m-\pi}^{4\pi m} \right] \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du.$$

Then using the 2π -periodicity of \cos , we get that

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \left[\int_0^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du + \int_{-\pi}^0 \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} G\left(\frac{u+4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{j=m+1}^{2m-1} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du \\ &= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=m+1}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G\left(\frac{u+4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du \end{aligned}$$

Since for $k_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $F(k_1, \cdot)$ is $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodic by part (i) of Lemma 3.24, we have that G is $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodic, and thus in particular $G\left(\frac{u+4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) = G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right)$. Hence, where $u = m\sqrt{3}k_2$

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \frac{1-\cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1-\cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} G(k_2) dk_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=m+1}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du. \end{aligned}$$

First & Third Terms: We now evaluate the first and third pairs of integrals on the right hand side of (3.26). Following a very similar chain of reasoning to that used in evaluating the second term above, we get that for $u = m\sqrt{3}k_2$

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_0^{k_2\sqrt{3}} \frac{1-\cos(nk_1)}{1-\cos(k_1)} \frac{1-\cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1-\cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} F(k) dk \\ &= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} G_1\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^\pi \frac{1-\cos(Mu)}{M(1-\cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G_1\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G_1\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] du, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{6\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_{k_2\sqrt{3}-4\pi}^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} F(k) \, dk \\
&= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} G_3 \left(\frac{u + 2\pi j + 4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G_3 \left(\frac{u + 4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G_3 \left(\frac{u + 6\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du.
\end{aligned}$$

We now sum the first and third terms evaluated above and utilise the $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodicity of F in k_2 . Firstly, for $j \in \{0, \dots, m\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
& G_1 \left(\frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) + G_3 \left(\frac{u + 4\pi m + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \\
&= \int_0^{\frac{u+2\pi j}{m}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F \left(k_1, \frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \, dk_1 + \int_{\frac{u+2\pi j}{m}}^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F \left(k_1, \frac{u + 4\pi m + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \, dk_1 \\
&= \int_0^{\frac{u+2\pi j}{m}} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F \left(k_1, \frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \, dk_1 + \int_{\frac{u+2\pi j}{m}}^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F \left(k_1, \frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \, dk_1 \\
&= \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F \left(k_1, \frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \, dk_1 = G \left(\frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, summing the first and third terms then yields, noting that $u = m\sqrt{3}k_2$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \left[\int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_0^{k_2\sqrt{3}} + \int_{\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}}^{\frac{6\pi}{\sqrt{3}}} \int_{k_2\sqrt{3}-4\pi}^{2\pi} \right] \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} \frac{1 - \cos(Mm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{M(1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} F(k) \, dk \\
&= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} G \left(\frac{u + 2\pi j + 4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G \left(\frac{u + 4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G \left(\frac{u + 6\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du
\end{aligned}$$

and now utilising the $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodicity of F in k_2 gives

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} G \left(\frac{u + 2\pi j + 4\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{4m\sqrt{3}} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G \left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G \left(\frac{u + 2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}} \right) \right] \, du
\end{aligned}$$

Sum of All Terms: We now sum all the integral terms together and in particular evaluate the required integral. Firstly

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \sum_{j=m+1}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] \\ & + \left[\mathbf{1}_{[0,\pi)} G\left(\frac{u}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) + \mathbf{1}_{[-\pi,0)} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi m}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \right] \\ & = \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by Lemma 3.21 and by the properties of F ,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{M} \langle d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m} \rangle &= \frac{1}{16\pi m} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(Mu)}{M(1 - \cos(u))} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du \\ &\stackrel{M \rightarrow \infty}{=} \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F\left(k_1, \frac{2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) dk_1. \end{aligned} \tag{3.29}$$

For brevity, for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$, let $r_j = \frac{2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}$. In the way we computed the analogous term to (3.29) in Theorem 3.20, we similarly write $F((k_1, r_j))$ as

$$F((k_1, r_j)) = F((0, r_j)) + [F((k_1, r_j)) - F((0, r_j))],$$

where $F((0, r_j)) = 2$ by part (ii) of Lemma 3.24 (since $F(0, 0)$ is not well defined, we understand the expression $F(0, 0)$ as $\lim_{k_1 \rightarrow 0} F((k_1, 0)) = 2$). Now

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{M} \langle d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m}, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_{grain}^{M,n,m} \rangle &= \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k_1, r_j) dk_1 \\ &= \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(0, r_j) dk_1 \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} [F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)] dk_1. \end{aligned}$$

Performing a similar computation to obtain the expression (3.23) yields

$$\frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(0, r_j) dk_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(k_1 n)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} dk_1 = \frac{n}{2} + \mathcal{O}(1).$$

To evaluate

$$\frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} [F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)] dk_1,$$

we perform an approximation. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} [F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)] dk_1 \\ &= \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{[F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)]}{1 - \cos(k_1)} dk_1 \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{16\pi m} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \cos(nk_1) \frac{[F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)]}{1 - \cos(k_1)} dk_1. \end{aligned}$$

We can indeed show that the value of $[F((k_1, p_j)) - F(0, r_j)] = [F((k_1, p_j)) - 2] = \mathcal{O}(k_1^2)$ when k_1 is close to 0, and furthermore, close to zero, by a Taylor expansion $\frac{1}{1 - \cos(k_1)} = \mathcal{O}(k_1^2)$ close to zero also. Due to this observation, we can see that

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \cos(nk_1) \frac{[F(k_1, r_j) - F(0, r_j)]}{1 - \cos(k_1)} dk_1 = \int_0^{2\pi} \cos(nk_1) dk_1 + \mathcal{O}(1),$$

which in the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the integral goes to zero by the Riemann-Lebesgue lemma. Putting everything together, we therefore get that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{\text{grain}}(n, m) = \frac{1}{32\pi\sqrt{3}m^2} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{2 - F((k_1, r_j))}{1 - \cos(k_1)} dk_1 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right). \quad (3.30)$$

The dominant contribution from (3.30) on the right hand side as $m \rightarrow \infty$ comes from the first term, in particular around the region of the singularity of $\frac{1}{1 - \cos(k_1)}$, i.e. about the region $(k_1, r_j) \in [-\varepsilon, \varepsilon]^2$ for any small $\varepsilon > 0$, where the integral in the region outside this is bounded uniformly by m since $\frac{1}{1 - \cos(k_1)}$ is bounded away from 0. In particular, Taylor expanding the cosine function with k_1 close to zero

$$1 - \cos(k_1) = \frac{k_1^2}{2} + \mathcal{O}(k_1^4)$$

and also by expanding $F(k)$ around $k = 0$ as before,

$$F(k) = 2 - \frac{16}{3} \frac{k_1^2 k_2^2}{|k|^4} + \mathcal{O}(|k|^2),$$

we find that, after letting $T_\varepsilon = \lfloor \sqrt{3}\varepsilon m / (2\pi) \rfloor$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{\text{grain}}(n, m) = \frac{4}{3\pi\sqrt{3}m^2} \sum_{j=0}^{T_\varepsilon} \int_0^\varepsilon \frac{r_j^2}{(k_1^2 + r_j^2)} dk_1 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right).$$

Then summing over j and integrating over k_1 , we deduce that as $m \rightarrow \infty$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{\text{grain}}(n, m) = \frac{\log m}{6\pi m} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{m}\right),$$

precisely as was required. \square

Remark 3.23

Equation (3.24) is the *Read-Shockley* law for the energy of a grain boundary, this is because, by replacing $\frac{1}{m}$ with θ , we obtain that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{\text{grain}}(n, \theta) = -\frac{1}{6\pi}\theta \log \theta + \mathcal{O}(\theta),$$

which is precisely the law discussed in the introduction. What is interesting here is the fact that this energy is asymptotically independent of the separation, M , among the two arrays of charges it consists of. This is because, since each grain boundary dislocation $q_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} = \mathcal{O}(M)$, one would expect the energy of the grain E_{grain} to be of order $\mathcal{O}(M)$ (since we have divided the energy already by M), but instead we have obtained a result that is of order $\mathcal{O}(1)$. This indicates that there is some hidden behaviour that is occurring in the inner product $\langle q, G^*BGq \rangle$, which is giving rise to this behaviour in order. A further investigation of this would be an interesting route to follow in future research.

We now present a proof of some useful properties of the function F defined in (3.21).

Lemma 3.24 (Properties of $F(k)$)

We prove two properties of the function F as defined in (3.21).

- (i) *For all $k_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ where the inverse of \hat{A} exists, the function $F(k_1, \cdot)$, is $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodic;*
- (ii) *For all $k_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ where the inverse of \hat{A} exists, $F(0, k_2) = 2$.*

Proof. By equation (3.21), for $k \in \mathbb{R}^2$, the function $F : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$F(k) = [(e^{-ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{ik \cdot a_3})a_3] \hat{A}^{-1}(k) [(e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3],$$

where

$$\hat{A}(k) = 2 \sum_{l=1}^3 (a_l \otimes a_l)(1 - \cos(k \cdot a_l)) \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}.$$

We prove the above two properties separately.

(i) Since

$$(k_1, k_2 + 4\pi/\sqrt{3}) \cdot a_l = \begin{cases} k \cdot a_l & \text{if } l = 1, \\ k \cdot a_l + 2\pi & \text{if } l = 2, \\ k \cdot a_l - 2\pi & \text{if } l = 3, \end{cases} \quad (3.31)$$

it directly follows that

$$\hat{A}((k_1, k_2 + 4\pi/\sqrt{3})) = \hat{A}(k),$$

and in particular that $\hat{A}^{-1}((k_1, k_2 + 4\pi/\sqrt{3})) = \hat{A}^{-1}(k)$, when it exists. Furthermore, by (3.31) and by the fact that $e^{2\pi i} = 1$, it follows that

$$P((k_1, k_2 + 4\pi/\sqrt{3})) = P(k),$$

and similarly $P(-(k_1, k_2 + 4\pi/\sqrt{3})) = P(-k)$, where

$$P(k) = [(e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3].$$

Putting the $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodicity of \hat{A} and P with respect to the second variable together yields the result that $F(k_1, \cdot)$ is $\frac{4\pi}{\sqrt{3}}$ -periodic for all $k_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, where the inverse of \hat{A} makes sense.

(ii) We now prove that $F(0, k_2) = 2$ for all $k_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ where the inverse of \hat{A} exists. Let $k_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ be as in the hypothesis. Then by the definition of \hat{A} , we see that

$$\hat{A}(0, k_2) = \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}\right)\right) \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefore

$$\hat{A}^{-1}(0, k_2) = \frac{1}{3 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}\right)\right)} \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Furthermore, for $P(k)$ as defined above, it is easy to see that

$$P(0, k_2) = (e^{i\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}} - 1) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefore, by putting everything together, we can see that

$$F(0, k_2) = (e^{-i\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}} - 1) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \hat{A}^{-1}(0, k_2) (e^{i\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}} - 1) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= 2 \left(1 - \cos \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}k_2}{2} \right) \right) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \hat{A}^{-1}(0, k_2) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = 2,$$

as required.

□

Chapter 4

Scaling Limits and Energy Representation

In this chapter, we continue in the framework of the two dimensional triangular lattice as in Chapter 3, but now study the Ariza-Ortiz energy as the lattice spacing between adjacent atoms tends to zero. More specifically, we make progress in showing that a candidate Γ -limit of the rescaled energy with respect to the lattice spacing exhibits a particular integral form by proving an intermediate result. This result highly suggests that the Γ -limit has an integral representation similar to the form (1.3). Showing that the Γ -limit has this specific integral representation is a highly sought after result and shall be the subject of future research, see Chapter 5 for a more in depth discussion on possible future avenues for research. Furthermore, we refer the reader to the texts [Bra02; Dal11] for an introduction into Γ -convergence.

4.1 Scaled Model

We begin the chapter by first defining a rescaled Ariza-Ortiz model of dislocations. Consider a triangular lattice with *lattice spacing* $\varepsilon > 0$ given by

$$\mathcal{L}_\varepsilon := \{ n_1 a_1^\varepsilon + n_2 a_2^\varepsilon \mid n_i \in \mathbb{Z}, i = 1, 2 \},$$

where $a_i^\varepsilon := \varepsilon a_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$, and where a_i are defined as in (3.1). For $p = 0, 1, 2$, denote by Ω_ε^p the corresponding p -forms, each respectively acting on the p -cells, E_p^ε . Then the collection $(E_0^\varepsilon, E_1^\varepsilon, E_2^\varepsilon)$ forms the scaled lattice cellular complex, which together with Ω_ε^p allows for computation on the scaled lattice \mathcal{L}_ε . Given a displacement-slip pair $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0 \times \Omega_\varepsilon^1$, the elastic energy corresponding to (u, σ) is given by the following Ariza-Ortiz energy (since we're assuming that our lattice is infinite, as before, we make the assumption

that u and σ disappear at infinity)

$$\mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{e \in E_1^\varepsilon} [(du(e) - \sigma(e)) \cdot \delta e]^2. \quad (4.1)$$

Furthermore, for $p = 0, 1, 2$ and for $\varphi, \psi \in \Omega_\varepsilon^p$, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, define the rescaled inner product as

$$\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle_\varepsilon := \sum_{e \in E_p^\varepsilon} \varphi(e) \cdot \psi(e),$$

Also, to be able to represent the scaled Ariza-Ortiz energy, (4.1), in inner product form, we first need to define a rescaled version of the interaction operator $B : \Omega^1 \rightarrow \Omega^1$ defined in (3.4). Thus, define by $B_\varepsilon : \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \rightarrow \Omega_\varepsilon^1$ the following operator: for $\varphi \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1$

$$B_\varepsilon \varphi(e) = \sum_{e' \in E_1^\varepsilon} \overline{B}_\varepsilon(e, e') \varphi(e'),$$

where $\overline{B}_\varepsilon : E_1^\varepsilon \times E_1^\varepsilon \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ such that

$$\overline{B}_\varepsilon(e, e') = \begin{cases} \delta e \otimes \delta e & \text{if } e = e', \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then, for $(u, \sigma) \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0 \times \Omega_\varepsilon^1$, the Ariza-Ortiz energy (4.2) can be written as

$$\mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \langle du - \sigma, B_\varepsilon(du - \sigma) \rangle_\varepsilon.$$

We should note that for $e, e' \in E_1^\varepsilon$, $\overline{B}_\varepsilon(e, e') = \varepsilon^2 \overline{B}(\frac{e}{\varepsilon}, \frac{e'}{\varepsilon})$ for \overline{B} defined as in (3.3), and thus heuristically $B_\varepsilon = \varepsilon^2 B$. Now, given a 2-form, $q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2$, we define the elastic energy corresponding to this 2-form and this lattice spacing by

$$E_\varepsilon(q) := \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma).$$

The general space dislocations that we're particularly interested in are those that, up to translation, correspond to the formation of grains, with lattice points $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\varepsilon$, that are connected, bounded domains with regularisable boundaries. Although, obtaining results for these types of dislocations is a long term goal and simpler dislocations will first be considered. To simplify matters, for each lattice spacing $\varepsilon > 0$, consider grains of the form $\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon = ([0, \varepsilon n] \times [0, \lfloor 1/\varepsilon \rfloor] + \tau) \cap \mathcal{L}_\varepsilon$, for some constant $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\tau = \lambda a_l^\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for some $\lambda \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $l = 1, 2, 3$. Now, for set $\mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\varepsilon$, define the following space of dislocations

that form the grain \mathcal{V}

$$\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{V}) := \{ q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2 \mid \exists \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \text{ s.t. } d\sigma = q, \text{ supp } \sigma \subseteq \mathcal{V}, \text{ supp } d\sigma \subseteq \partial\mathcal{V} \},$$

where we use the convention that for $e \in E_1^\varepsilon$, $e \in \mathcal{V}$ if $e = [x, y]$ and $x, y \in \mathcal{V}$, and for $f \in E_2^\varepsilon$, $f \in \mathcal{V}$ if at least one of the edges, 1-cells, that make up f , i.e. $e \succ f$ is such that $e \in \mathcal{V}$. The particular set of dislocations that we shall be dealing with, i.e. the ones that correspond to the formation of grains \mathcal{G}_ε , lie in the set $\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon)$. For brevity, let $\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon = \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon)$. The reason why grains for the form \mathcal{G}_ε are being considered is because, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, the grain \mathcal{G}_ε is generated by dislocations, up to *gauge invariance*, of the form $q_{\text{grain}, \varepsilon}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, n, m}(f) = \varepsilon q_{\text{grain}}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, m, n}(f/\varepsilon)$ for $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $f \in E_2^\varepsilon$.

Lemma 4.1 (Closure of \mathcal{D}_ε under addition)

For all $\varepsilon > 0$, the space $\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G})$ is closed under addition, for any set $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$.

Proof. Let $q_i \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G})$ for $i = 1, 2$. Then, by definition of $\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G})$, there exist $\sigma_i \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1$ such that $d\sigma_i = q_i$, and for $i = 1, 2$

$$\text{supp } \sigma_i \subseteq \mathcal{G} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{supp } d\sigma_i \subseteq \partial\mathcal{G}.$$

Now, by linearity of d , $q_1 + q_2 = d(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{supp } (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) &\subseteq \text{supp } \sigma_1 \cup \text{supp } \sigma_2 \subseteq \mathcal{G}, \\ \text{supp } (d(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)) &\subseteq \text{supp } d\sigma_1 \cup \text{supp } d\sigma_2 \subseteq \partial\mathcal{G}, \end{aligned}$$

and hence we have that $q_1 + q_2 \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G})$. □

Measure Representation: To study the energy of dislocations as the lattice spacing is varied, it is useful to consider each dislocation as a measure. In particular, define the operator $\Phi : \Omega_\varepsilon^2 \rightarrow \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$, which represents 2-forms $q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2$ in measure form, i.e.

$$\Phi(q) := \sum_{f \in E_2^\varepsilon} q(f) \delta_{c(f)}, \quad q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2$$

where $c(f) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes the coordinate of the centre of the face $f \in E_2^\varepsilon$ and δ denotes the standard Dirac delta measure. Now, denote by X_ε the space of measures $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$ such that there exists a 2-form $q \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$ with $\mu = \Phi(q)$, i.e. $X_\varepsilon = \text{im } \Phi|_{\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon}$, so

$$X_\varepsilon = \{ \mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2) \mid \exists q \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon, \text{ s.t. } \mu = \Phi(q) \}.$$

The mapping $\Psi : \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon \rightarrow X_\varepsilon; q \mapsto \Phi(q)$ is invertible, thus, for any $\mu \in X_\varepsilon$, denote by $\Psi^{-1}(\mu) \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$ the unique 2-form such that $\mu = \Phi(\Psi^{-1}(\mu))$. For brevity we use a subscript

notation, i.e. for $q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2$, let $\mu_q := \Phi(q)$, and for $\mu \in X_\varepsilon$, we let $q_\mu := \Psi^{-1}(\mu)$.

Rescaling the Energy The aim of this chapter is to study the energy E_ε as the lattice spacing ε goes to zero. For this to yield a result that makes sense in the limit as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, we first need to rescale the energy E_ε so that it is of order $\mathcal{O}(1)$ with respect to the lattice spacing ε . We shall specifically study dislocations that form grains of the form \mathcal{G}_ε , and this corresponds to 2-forms defined as $q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m}$. Thus, given that, by a rescaled version of (3.15), where the proof is identical, for any $q \in \Omega_\varepsilon^2$, we may define the energy E_ε purely with respect to q as

$$E_\varepsilon(q) = \frac{1}{2} \langle q, G_\varepsilon^* B_\varepsilon G_\varepsilon q \rangle_\varepsilon$$

where $G_\varepsilon = (1 - dA^{-1}d^*B_\varepsilon)d^*\Delta^{-1}$ is the Greens function and $G_\varepsilon^* = \Delta^{-1}d(1 - B_\varepsilon dA^{-1}d^*)$ is its adjoint. In particular, for $q \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$, i.e. $q = q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m}$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\begin{aligned} E_\varepsilon(q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, n, m}) &= \frac{1}{2} \langle q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^\varepsilon, G_\varepsilon^* B_\varepsilon G_\varepsilon q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{f \in E_\varepsilon^2} q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^\varepsilon \cdot G_\varepsilon^* B_\varepsilon G_\varepsilon q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m} \\ &= \underbrace{\sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor - 1} q_{\text{dip},\varepsilon}^n(f - mj(a_2^\varepsilon - a_3^\varepsilon))}_{\mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{\varepsilon})} \cdot \underbrace{G_\varepsilon^* B_\varepsilon G_\varepsilon}_{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)} \underbrace{q_{\text{dip},\varepsilon}^n(f - mj(a_2^\varepsilon - a_3^\varepsilon))}_{\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)} \\ &= \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, to be able to take limits as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and for them to yield interesting results, we introduce a *rescaled* energy functional $\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon : \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$, which for each $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu) := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3} E_\varepsilon(q_\mu) & \text{if } \mu \in X_\varepsilon, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

Now, by $\mathcal{Q} \subseteq \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$, define the space of measures which can be obtained via a weak limit of measures corresponding to desirable dislocations as the lattice spacing $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, i.e.

$$\mathcal{Q} := \left\{ \mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2) \mid \text{for all } \varepsilon > 0, \exists \mu_\varepsilon \in X_\varepsilon \text{ s.t. } \mu_\varepsilon \rightharpoonup \mu \right\}.$$

For each $\varepsilon > 0$, having now defined a rescaled energy \mathcal{E}_ε , we aim to study the Γ -limit of \mathcal{E}_ε as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. To be able to do this, it is useful to first have in mind an ansatz Γ -limit, ideally in integral form. It is not obvious what the Γ -limit of \mathcal{E}_ε will look like as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, but it is highly suspected that it will resemble a form similar to (1.3). However,

motivated by the definition of Γ -convergence, we shall define an ansatz for the Γ -limit, $\mathcal{E} : \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$, in (4.3) by

$$\mathcal{E}(\mu) = \begin{cases} \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_\varepsilon) & \text{if } \mu \in \mathcal{Q}, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

4.2 Integral Representation of Limiting Energy

The function \mathcal{E} , defined in (4.3), represents the limiting continuum energy of dislocations obtained as a limit of the scaled Ariza-Ortiz energy defined in (4.2). This energy functional has been obtained from a fully discrete model developed in Chapters 2 and 3, and to the best knowledge of the author, functionals of this form have not yet been studied in literature for the triangular lattice structure. The paper [Pon07] has performed a similar analysis, although for square lattices, and furthermore papers such as [Fan18; GLP10] have obtained similar Γ -limits, but via *semi-discrete dislocation models*, where the atomic scale is brought in via an internal scale known as the *core radius*. In this section, we move on to the main topic of this chapter and of this thesis in which we show that, for a specific set of singular measures, the functional \mathcal{E} , is additive. This makes progress in showing that the energy \mathcal{E} has a particular integral representation. We begin by first explicitly defining what it means for two measures to be singular.

Definition 4.2 (Singular)

If $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$ are two σ -finite measures on the same σ -algebra, \mathcal{B} , of subsets of \mathbb{R}^2 , then μ and ν are said to be *singular* if there exists two sets $A, B \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$, $A \cup B = \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\mu(B \cap E) = \nu(A \cap E) = 0$ for all $E \in \mathcal{B}$.

Before proving the discussed additivity result, we first prove the following lemma which will be useful in obtaining the result of Lemma 4.4.

Lemma 4.3

Let $f \in C^1(-\pi, \pi)$. Then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n(1 - \cos(x))} f(x) \, dx = 0.$$

Proof. We note that the value $n \in \mathbb{N}$ used in this statement is independent of the value of n of the width of grains \mathcal{G}_ε defined before. Now, the Laurent expansion of $\frac{1}{1 - \cos(x)}$ on the domain $\Upsilon := (-\pi, \pi) \setminus \{0\}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{1 - \cos(x)} &= \sum_{n=-1}^{\infty} a_n x^{2n} = \frac{2}{x^2} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^{2n} \\ &= \frac{2}{x^2} + g(x) \end{aligned}$$

where $a_n \in \mathbb{R}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $x \in (-\pi, \pi) \setminus \{0\}$ and $g : (-\pi, \pi) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$; $x \mapsto \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^{2n}$.¹ The function g given is the g obtained when after removing the removable singularity at 0. Since g is continuous and $\Upsilon \cup \{0\}$ is bounded, g is also bounded. Therefore for the function f given in the hypothesis

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n(1 - \cos(x))} f(x) \, dx &= 2 \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{nx^2} f(x) \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n} f(x) g(x) \, dx. \end{aligned}$$

Now, changing variables via $u = nx$

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{nx^2} f(x) \, dx = \int_{-n\pi}^{n\pi} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u^2} f\left(\frac{u}{n}\right) \, du$$

and using the standard mean value theorem to write $f\left(\frac{u}{n}\right) = f(0) + f'\left(\xi\left(\frac{u}{n}\right)\right) \frac{u}{n}$ for some continuous function $\xi : (-\pi, \pi) \rightarrow (-\pi, \pi)$, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_{-n\pi}^{n\pi} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u^2} f(0) \, du \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{n} \int_{-n\pi}^{n\pi} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u} f'\left(\xi\left(\frac{u}{n}\right)\right) \, du. \end{aligned}$$

Now it is easy to show that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u^2} f(0) \, du = 0.$$

Furthermore, $\frac{\cos(u)(1 - \cos(u))}{u}$ is bounded on $(-\pi, \pi)$ and since $f \in C^1(-\pi, \pi)$, f' is also bounded on $(-\pi, \pi)$, and in particular $|f'\left(\xi\left(\frac{u}{n}\right)\right)| \leq C$ for some constant $C > 0$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\pi, \pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{nx^2} f(x) \, dx &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u^2} f(0) \, du \\ &\quad + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \int_{-n\pi}^{n\pi} \cos(u) \frac{1 - \cos(u)}{u} f'\left(\xi\left(\frac{u}{n}\right)\right) \, du \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

It now remains is to show that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n} f(x) g(x) \, dx = 0.$$

¹The domain Υ has been chosen in such a way since this is the domain in which the Laurent series is convergent.

Letting $h := fg$, we have that $h \in C^1(-\pi, \pi)$, h is bounded on $(-\pi, \pi)$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n} f(x)g(x) \, dx \\ = \frac{1}{n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx)h(x) \, dx - \frac{1}{n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos^2(nx)h(x) \, dx. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\cos^2(\gamma) = \frac{1}{2}(\cos(2\gamma) + 1)$ for $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(nx)h(x) \, dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2n} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(2nx)h(x) \, dx - \frac{1}{2n} \int_{(-\pi, \pi)} h(x) \, dx. \end{aligned}$$

By the Riemann-Lebesgue lemma, we know that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(kx)h(x) \, dx = 0,$$

and therefore, since h is bounded, we get that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{(-\pi, \pi)} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n} f(x)g(x) \, dx = 0.$$

Putting all the above results together, yields the desired result, i.e.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{(-\pi, \pi)} \cos(nx) \frac{1 - \cos(nx)}{n(1 - \cos(x))} f(x) \, dx = 0.$$

□

Using Lemma 4.3, we now prove that \mathcal{E} is additive under specific singular measures. By the definition of \mathcal{E} , additivity of \mathcal{E} for all $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2) \setminus \mathcal{Q}$ with $\mu_1 \perp \mu_2$ holds trivially, therefore it remains to be concerned with the space \mathcal{Q} .

Lemma 4.4

Let $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in \mathcal{Q}$ such that $\mu_1 \perp \mu_2$. For each $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\mu_i^\varepsilon \in X_\varepsilon$ such that $\mu_i^\varepsilon \rightharpoonup \mu_i$ as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, with $i = 1, 2$. In particular, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists q_i^ε such that $\mu_i^\varepsilon = \mu_{q_i^\varepsilon}$ and $q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon = q_{\text{grain}, \varepsilon}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, n, m}$ for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Assuming that each q_i^ε forms half of $q_{\text{grain}, \varepsilon}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, n, m}$ in the vertical direction, then the following additive decomposition of the functional \mathcal{E} holds

$$\mathcal{E}(\mu_1 + \mu_2) = \mathcal{E}(\mu_1) + \mathcal{E}(\mu_2).$$

Proof. Let $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in \mathcal{Q}$ be such that $\mu_1 \perp \mu_2$, then, by the definition of \mathcal{Q} , there exist

sequences $\mu_1^\varepsilon, \mu_2^\varepsilon \in X_\varepsilon$ such that

$$\mu_1^\varepsilon \rightharpoonup \mu_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_2^\varepsilon \rightharpoonup \mu_2, \quad \text{as } \varepsilon \rightarrow 0.$$

Since for $i = 1, 2$, $\mu_i^\varepsilon \in X_\varepsilon$, there exists $q_i^\varepsilon \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$ such that $\mu_i^\varepsilon = \mu_{q_i^\varepsilon}$. By definition

$$\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon = \mu_{q_1^\varepsilon} + \mu_{q_2^\varepsilon} = \sum_{f \in E_\varepsilon^2} (q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon)(f) \delta_{c(f)},$$

then, by Lemma 4.1, we have that $q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon \in \mathcal{D}_\varepsilon$, and therefore $\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon = \mu_{q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon}$. Thus for each $\varepsilon > 0$, $\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon \in X_\varepsilon$, and $\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon \rightharpoonup \mu_1 + \mu_2$ as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Hence

$$\mathcal{E}(\mu_1 + \mu_2) = \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon).$$

By definition, for each $\varepsilon > 0$

$$\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3} E_\varepsilon(q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon),$$

where

$$E_\varepsilon(q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon) = \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma).$$

Now, if we let $\tilde{\sigma} = \sigma_1^\varepsilon + \sigma_2^\varepsilon \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1$, where $\sigma_i^\varepsilon \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1$ are such that $d\sigma_i^\varepsilon = q_i^\varepsilon$, which exist by the definition of \mathcal{D}_ε , then $d\tilde{\sigma} = q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon$. Then, due to gauge invariance of the Ariza-Ortiz energy (4.1) and by an \mathcal{L}_ε lattice version of Corollary 3.13, where the proof is identical, for any $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) = \min_{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \tilde{\sigma}) = \frac{1}{2} \langle \tilde{\sigma}, B_\varepsilon \tilde{\sigma} \rangle_\varepsilon - \frac{1}{2} \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \tilde{\sigma}, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \tilde{\sigma} \rangle_\varepsilon.$$

Since $\sigma_1^\varepsilon + \sigma_2^\varepsilon = \tilde{\sigma}$ and $d\sigma_i^\varepsilon = q_i^\varepsilon$, we can further decompose into

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) &= \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) + \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle \sigma_1^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle \sigma_2^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon - \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon - \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right]. \end{aligned}$$

To prove the result of the lemma for these specific types of dislocations, it suffices to show that the mixed terms, in the square brackets above, disappear.

By the definition of $\mathcal{D}_\varepsilon(\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon)$, we can assume that up to *gauge equivalence*, for some $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon = q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m},$$

where $M = \lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor$ and

$$q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{M,n,m}(f) = \varepsilon q_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} \left(\frac{f}{\varepsilon} \right), \quad f \in E_2^\varepsilon.$$

Since μ_1 and μ_2 are singular, the q_i^ε 's are in a sense *disjoint*, i.e. their dislocation points do not intersect. To simplify calculations, in the hypothesis of the lemma, we have assumed that the q_i^ε 's each respectively consist of only half of $q_{\text{grain},\varepsilon}^{\lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor, n, m}$. In particular, for $f \in E_2^\varepsilon$, we let

$$q_1^\varepsilon(f) = \varepsilon q_1 \left(\frac{f}{\varepsilon} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad q_2^\varepsilon(f) = \varepsilon q_2 \left(\frac{f}{\varepsilon} \right),$$

where, for $b \in E_2$

$$q_1(b) := \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor} q_{\text{dip}}^n(b - (j-1)m(a_2 - a_3)), \quad q_2(b) := \sum_{j=\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor + 1}^M q_{\text{dip}}^n(b - (j-1)m(a_2 - a_3)).$$

Then, up to a lattice valued 0-form, the following 1-forms, σ_1^ε and σ_2^ε each respectively generate the 2-forms q_1^ε and q_2^ε in the sense $d\sigma_i^\varepsilon = q_i^\varepsilon$ for $i = 1, 2$. In particular, for $x, x' \in \mathcal{L}_\varepsilon$

$$\sigma_1^\varepsilon(x, x') = \varepsilon \sigma_1 \left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon}, \frac{x'}{\varepsilon} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_2^\varepsilon(x, x') = \varepsilon \sigma_2 \left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon}, \frac{x'}{\varepsilon} \right)$$

where, for $y, y' \in \mathcal{L}$ (i.e. $\varepsilon = 1$)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1(y, y') &= \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor} \sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(y + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3), y' + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3)), \\ \sigma_2(y, y') &= \sum_{j=\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor + 1}^M \sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(y + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3), y' + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3)). \end{aligned}$$

Now, since for $e \in E_1^\varepsilon$

$$\begin{aligned} B_\varepsilon \sigma_\varepsilon(e) &= \sum_{e' \in E_1^\varepsilon} \bar{B}_\varepsilon(e, e') \sigma_\varepsilon(e') \\ &= \varepsilon^2 \cdot \varepsilon \sum_{e' \in E_1^\varepsilon} \bar{B}(e/\varepsilon, e'/\varepsilon) \sigma(e'/\varepsilon) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \varepsilon^3 B\sigma(e/\varepsilon),$$

it follows that

$$\langle \sigma_1^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon = \sum_{e \in E_1^\varepsilon} \sigma_1^\varepsilon \cdot B\sigma_2^\varepsilon = \varepsilon^4 \langle \sigma_1, B\sigma_2 \rangle_1.$$

Furthermore, through a similar computation, we arrive at, for $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$

$$\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_i^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_j^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon = \varepsilon^4 \langle d^* B\sigma_i, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_j \rangle_1.$$

Due to this, in the following, to simplify matters, we consider calculations with σ_i only, and then multiply by the rescaling parameter as necessary. Also, for brevity, in the following, we denote $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_1$ by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$.

Disappearance of Mixed Terms: Recall that, by Example 3.7,

$$q_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(f) = \sum_{j=1}^M q_{\text{dip}}^n(f - (j-1)m(a_2 - a_3)), \quad f \in E_2.$$

where

$$q_{\text{dip}}^n(f) = (\mathbf{1}_{f_0}(f) - \mathbf{1}_{f_n}(f))a_1, \quad f \in E_2$$

and $f_j = (0, a_1, -a_3) + ja_1$ for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Furthermore, by the same example, for $x, x' \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}(x, x') = \sum_{j=1}^M \sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(x + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3), x' + m(j-1)(a_2 - a_3)),$$

where for $x \in \mathcal{L}$

$$\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} a_1 & \text{if } l = 2 \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ -a_1 & \text{if } l = 3 \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In particular, we have that $d\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m} = q_{\text{grain}}^{M,n,m}$ and $d\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n = q_{\text{dip}}^n$. Now, recalling the results of Chapter 3, we have that

$$B\sigma_{\text{dip}}^n(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2}a_2 & \text{if } l = 2 \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ \frac{1}{2}a_3 & \text{if } l = 3 \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then through a calculation, it can be shown that for $x \in \mathcal{L}$ with x in the supporting lattice points of each the σ_i 's respectively

$$B\sigma_1(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2} \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor a_2 & \text{if } l = 2 \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor a_3 & \text{if } l = 3 \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$B\sigma_2(x, x + a_l) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2} (M - \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor) a_2 & \text{if } l = 2 \text{ and } x = ja_1 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ \frac{1}{2} (M - \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor) a_3 & \text{if } l = 3 \text{ and } x = ja_1 - a_3 \text{ for some } j \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Now, since the supports of σ_1 and σ_2 do not intersect, it is easy to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \sigma_i, B\sigma_j \rangle &= \sum_{e \in E_1} \sum_{e' \in E_1} \sigma_i(e) \cdot B(e, e') \sigma_j(e') \\ &= \sum_{e \in E_1} \sigma_i(e) \cdot (\delta e \otimes \delta e) \sigma_j(e), \end{aligned}$$

for $i, j = 1, 2$ with $i \neq j$. We are now left with the study of the sum

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_1, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_2 \rangle + \langle d^* B\sigma_2, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_1 \rangle.$$

For this, as we did in Chapter 3, we shall convert to Fourier space to make the calculations easier by using Definition 3.17. Since σ_1 is defined as $\sigma_{\text{grain}}^{\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor, n, m}$, it directly follows that

$$\widehat{d^* B\sigma_1}(k) = \left[-\frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \right] \left[\frac{e^{-i \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1}{e^{-im \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1} \right] \left[\frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right] P(k),$$

where $P(k) = (e^{ik \cdot a_2} - 1)a_2 - (1 - e^{-ik \cdot a_3})a_3$. Through a similar computation that was done to obtain the above expression, we have that

$$\widehat{d^* B\sigma_2}(k) = e^{i \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m \sqrt{3} k_2} \left[-\frac{e^{ik_1}}{2} \right] \left[\frac{e^{-i(M - \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor) m \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1}{e^{-im \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1} \right] \left[\frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right] P(k).$$

Whence

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d^* B\sigma_1, A^{-1} d^* B\sigma_2 \rangle &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{\widehat{d^* B\sigma_1}(k)} \cdot \hat{A}^{-1}(k) \widehat{d^* B\sigma_2} dk \\ &= \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \left| \frac{e^{ink_1} - 1}{e^{ik_1} - 1} \right|^2 \left[\frac{e^{i \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1}{e^{im \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1} \right] \left[\frac{e^{-i(M - \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor) m \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1}{e^{-im \sqrt{3} k_2} - 1} \right] e^{i \lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m \sqrt{3} k_2} F(k) dk \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \frac{\left[e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] \left[e^{-i(M-\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2}}{2(1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2))} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk.$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] \left[e^{-i(M-\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] \\ &= e^{-i(M-2\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} - e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2} - e^{-i(M-\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Since $M \in \mathbb{N}$, M is either of the form $M = 2p$ or $M = 2p + 1$ for some $p \in \mathbb{N}_0$, and in both cases $\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor = p$. If $M = 2p$, i.e. M is even, then

$$\left[e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] \left[e^{-i(M-\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] = 2 - 2\cos(pm\sqrt{3}k_2).$$

If $M = 2p + 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[e^{i\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] \left[e^{-i(M-\lfloor \frac{M}{2} \rfloor)m\sqrt{3}k_2} - 1 \right] = e^{-im\sqrt{3}k_2} - e^{ipm\sqrt{3}k_2} - e^{-i(p+1)m\sqrt{3}k_2} + 1 \\ &= 4e^{-\frac{im\sqrt{3}k_2}{2}} \sin((p+1)m\sqrt{3}k_2) \sin(pm\sqrt{3}k_2). \end{aligned}$$

For the sake of convenience, assume that M is even, in which case, we have that

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_1, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_2 \rangle = \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} e^{i\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2} \frac{1 - \cos(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk. \quad (4.4)$$

Similarly, continuing on the assumption that M is even, we show that

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_2, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_1 \rangle = \frac{1}{4|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} e^{-i\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2} \frac{1 - \cos(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk. \quad (4.5)$$

Summing (4.4) and (4.5) yields

$$\langle d^* B\sigma_1, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_2 \rangle + \langle d^* B\sigma_2, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_1 \rangle \quad (4.6)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \cos\left(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2\right) \frac{1 - \cos(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk, \quad (4.7)$$

and after letting $N = \frac{M}{2}$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle d^* B\sigma_1, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_2 \rangle + \langle d^* B\sigma_2, A^{-1}d^* B\sigma_1 \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \cos\left(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2\right) \frac{1 - \cos(\frac{M}{2}m\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk \\ &= \frac{1}{2|\mathcal{B}|} \int_{\mathcal{B}} \cos\left(Nm\sqrt{3}k_2\right) \frac{1 - \cos(Nm\sqrt{3}k_2)}{1 - \cos(m\sqrt{3}k_2)} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k) \, dk \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, changing variables via $u = m\sqrt{3}k_2$, through a similar computation performed in Chapter 3 to obtain the energy of two infinite parallel walls, we obtain that

$$= \frac{1}{8\pi m} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(Nu) \frac{1 - \cos(Nu)}{1 - \cos(u)} \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u + 2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right) du,$$

where, for $\eta \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$G(\eta) := \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1 - \cos(nk_1)}{1 - \cos(k_1)} F(k_1, \eta) dk_1.$$

In particular, we have obtained that

$$\langle d^* B \sigma_1, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_2 \rangle_1 + \langle d^* B \sigma_2, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_1 \rangle_1 = \frac{1}{8\pi m} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(Nu) \frac{1 - \cos(Nu)}{1 - \cos(u)} \mathcal{Z}(u) du,$$

where $\mathcal{Z}(u) := \sum_{j=0}^{2m-1} G\left(\frac{u+2\pi j}{m\sqrt{3}}\right)$, is a continuous function away from its singularity at zero which is analytic (and hence differentiable).²

Reverting Back to Scaled Form: Therefore, returning the scaling parameter ε back into the mix, we obtain that

$$\langle \sigma_i^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_j^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon = \varepsilon^4 \langle \sigma_i, B \sigma_j \rangle_1 = 0, \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2 \text{ with } i \neq j.$$

Furthermore,

$$\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon^4}{8\pi m} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(Nu) \frac{1 - \cos(Nu)}{1 - \cos(u)} \mathcal{Z}(u) du$$

Now, since $M = 2N$ and $M = \lfloor \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \rfloor$, it follows that $\varepsilon \sim \frac{1}{2N}$. In particular, with equality up to a constant, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right] \\ & \approx \frac{1}{16\pi m} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos(Nu) \frac{1 - \cos(Nu)}{N(1 - \cos(u))} \mathcal{Z}(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

Then, by Lemma 4.3, it follows that in the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and hence $N \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right] = 0. \quad (4.8)$$

²This follows by the properties of F , defined in (3.21), discussed in Chapter 3.

Additivity of Energy: By (4.8) and the result that $\langle \sigma_1^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle = 0 = \langle \sigma_2^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle$ to all $\varepsilon > 0$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
E(q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon) &= \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon + q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) \\
&= \left[\min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) + \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle \sigma_1^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle \sigma_2^\varepsilon, B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon - \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon - \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right] \\
&= \left[\min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) + \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right].
\end{aligned}$$

That is

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon) &= \frac{1}{\varepsilon^3} \left[\min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_1^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) + \min_{\substack{u \in \Omega_\varepsilon^0, \sigma \in \Omega_\varepsilon^1 \\ d\sigma = q_2^\varepsilon}} \mathcal{H}_\varepsilon(u, \sigma) \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle + \langle d^* B \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle \right], \\
&= \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon) + \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_2^\varepsilon) - \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, taking the limit inferior of both sides as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{E}(\mu_1 + \mu_2) &= \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon + \mu_2^\varepsilon) \\
&= \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left[\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon) + \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_2^\varepsilon) - \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

using (4.8), we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} [\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon) + \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_2^\varepsilon)] \\
&\quad - \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^3} \left[\langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon + \langle d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_2^\varepsilon, A^{-1} d^* B_\varepsilon \sigma_1^\varepsilon \rangle_\varepsilon \right] \\
&= \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} [\mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon) + \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_2^\varepsilon)].
\end{aligned}$$

One can then show that in this case, the limit inferior can be considered as a standard limit, which yields

$$= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_1^\varepsilon) + \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{E}_\varepsilon(\mu_2^\varepsilon)$$

$$= \mathcal{E}(\mu_1) + \mathcal{E}(\mu_2),$$

precisely what we wanted to show. □

Obtaining Lemma 4.4 strongly suggests the the integral representation result of interest does indeed hold true. To further support this conjecture, the next step would be to prove Lemma 4.4 for *all* singular measures on $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2; \mathbb{R}^2)$. We believe that obtaining this result will be very similar to having obtained the result of the above lemma. The difficulty then lies in proving a general integral representation theorem, in which the structure of grains is not as explicitly defined, but instead just a bounded connected domain with a regularisable boundary.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

In this thesis, we have provided the set up, and have also performed some vital calculations in studying dislocations from a fully discrete atomistic model. Using [AO05], in Chapter 2, we have fully formulated the discrete theory of crystal mechanics in the sense of algebraic topology and exterior differential calculus. Furthermore, in Chapter 3, following the works of [GT19] we have proved a number of properties of the elastic energy of dislocations, in particular that it satisfies a decomposition into energies that respectively depend on purely elastic energy and also the energy contribution from dislocations. We have further shown and demonstrated via a calculation that the Ariza-Ortiz energy does indeed accurately model grains and the energy of grain boundaries, by showing that a Read-Shockley law is satisfied for small angle tilt grain boundaries produced by two infinite walls of dislocations. In Chapter 4, we have then extended this theory of the Ariza-Ortiz energy to an arbitrary lattice spacing and have made progress into showing that the continuum energy that is obtained via a Γ -limit of the Ariza-Ortiz energy has a specific integral representation. To the best knowledge of the author, the results of Chapter 4 have not yet been shown in literature for a two dimensional triangular lattice.

With regards to the topics of future research, an obvious choice would be to complete and also to extend to larger spaces the theory of obtaining an integral representation of the limiting Ariza-Ortiz energy considered in Chapter 4. Since the proofs of Chapter 4 relied on a specific structure of dislocations, it is likely that a new approach will be required to deduce the general result of an integral representation of the limiting energy, however the results of Chapter 4 have provided strong evidence that the result does indeed hold true. Furthermore, for interests of mathematical completion, once an integral representation is obtained, it would be desirable to prove that the limiting Ariza-Ortiz energy dubbed as the *ansatz for the Γ -limit* is indeed the Γ -limit of the energy \mathcal{E}_ε as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. From here, one could continue and repeat the results on either higher dimensional domains, or on more complex lattice structures, to contribute to the development of this theory. The main drawback of the current Ariza-Ortiz energy is that it only considers

static lattices. What would be of particular interest is to further the Ariza-Ortiz model of dislocations by incorporating temperature into the model. This would greatly increase the difficulty of this problem, but a result of this calibre would be highly desirable. However, this would be a long term goal and many steps still need to be taken before a complete theory involving finite temperature is presented.

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